

40. To achieve global nuclear disarmament, the U.S. must reveal the truth: the atomic bombing of Hiroshima and Nagasaki were absolutely fictional and successful psychological warfare

—An economic analysis of war behavior of the U.S. and Russia in terms of large-scale reduction of nuclear weapons.

Should U.S.-China Relations Be Normalized: A Historical, Religious, and Philosophical Perspective

1

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Catalogues

1. Chinese civilization and fictional ancient European Civilization
 2. The religious, cultural, customs and beliefs of Chinese civilization are different from the religious, cultural, customs and beliefs brought about by the fictional Bible in Europe.
 - 3. Suggest a global discussion on canceling counterfeit Easter and Christmas**
 - 4. Tesla Electric Car's Millimeter Radar Defeats False Bible to Verify Chinese Religious Culture**
 5. The cultivation of American political leaders and religious culture
 6. The history of China's contributions to the United States and the harm of the U.S. to China
 7. Since 1784, China has assisted the U.S. for the first time, friendly China saved the early United States, which was blocked by Britain and Spain
 8. Friendly China helped the U.S. accumulate wealth to expand its territory, but the U.S. dumped opium to China. Is this a friend? Does the United States have a conscience?
 9. China helped the United States for the second time in the 1860
 10. China's third assistance to the United States
 11. The United States struck the deadliest fourth blow against China
 12. China's fifth aid to the United States
 13. The United States launched its destructive sixth strike against China
 - 14. The bombing of China by the US military led to China's participation in the Korean War that began in 1950**
 15. In the early 1970s, the United States used its 13th strike against China
 16. Comparison of prisoners of war ethics between China, Japan, and the U.S.
 17. Looking at China-U.S. relations from Japan's religious behavior toward the U.S.
 18. Forged Thucydides Trap creating political confrontation between the U.S. and China
 19. Forged Thucydides Trap creating economic confrontation Between the U.S. and China
- The social system that saves humanity – an optimized and improved version of the Equal-Field system of the early Tang Dynasty.**

20. The incident of President George H.W. Bush vomiting at a state dinner shows that the majority of Americans do not have genuine religious beliefs, unlike the Chinese people.

21. Would you want your son or daughter be classmates with a serial killer? Is it appropriate for the United States to ally with a **devil who committed seventy massacres in Hunan Province** to suppress a just nation?

22. Cooperation between the United States and China should not be entangled with China's political system. The ruling party in China is different from any other ruling party in the world.

23. From a historical, philosophical, and logical perspective, the secrets and irreplicable reasons for the success of the American economic system and model

24. Complete capitalization of assets, complete financial and economic freedom, and the 20/80 law, universal values, Christian doctrine, the Bible, and the firewall

25. The catastrophic losses caused by the extremely bad and evil Japan's invasion of China and the enormous opportunities brought to US-China cooperation in compensation claims

26. Regarding the proposal to donate ancient Chinese artifacts to the hometowns of 30 global friends and establish museums: Considerations for activating the "One Belt, One Road" initiative through a "Tourism Behavioral Economy" in the U.S.

27. From a historical, religious, political, and economic perspective, is it right or wrong for the United States to protect Taiwan?

28. Westerners often discriminate against Chinese people based on their skin color, but Europeans and Americans have skin colors that resemble yellow people more than Chinese people.

29. From **the extremely bad and evil Japan's sinister immigration invasion policy and inhumane drug cultivation policy** towards China, which country is more suitable to be a friend?

30. China-US cooperation claims proposal, the United States resolves the debt crisis.

31. Quantitative Historical Comparative Analysis of the Nature of Japanese People and Whether Japan is Worthy of Trust and Assistance

—— Qualitative and Quantitative Analysis of the Evil Japanese Massacre and Property Robbery

32. The United States should help China figure out **how many Chinese children were transported to Japan** by the Japanese and **how many were eaten by extremely bad and evil Japanese around the world.**

33. Analysis of the total number of Chinese people slaughtered by the the extremely bad and evil Japanese invaders around the world

34. Historical reference period for current political-economic systems in China and the U.S., and trends in future global social systems

—— Evaluating market-oriented systems, social systems in China and the U.S. from the perspective of the excellent Equal-Field system in the ancient history of China

35. Religious thoughts in the Tang Dynasty, China's religious beliefs, culture, values, and protection of religious deities for the people

36. Returning to the Bible to discuss China-U.S. relations

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37. The U.S. government should immediately release innocent electrical engineering Ph.D. professor Zhang Hao, and sentence the false accuser to death or more than three times imprisonment.

38. American lawyers forming a legal team to sue Taiwanese murderers may pave the way for a milestone in U.S.-China relations.

39. All parties should promote the Taiwanese soldiers and warriors' uprising to pass the quasi-peaceful behavior to eliminate the evil pseudo-government and punish the criminals, and achieve the reunification of China.

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——An economic analysis of war behavior of the U.S. and Russia in terms of large-scale reduction of nuclear weapons.

41. Russia's future strategy under pressure from the U.S., NATO, and Japan, as well as China-Russian relations

42. The grave impact of the Middle East situation on U.S.-China relations, and the future after Israel's mass killing of civilians.

43. China's Repeated Lunar Sampling and U.S. Government Ethics, the US government should immediately acknowledge that false moon landings are part of psychological warfare.

44. The Catholic Church, using missionaries such as Matteo Ricci, falsified identities to steal the original Chinese copyright of the mathematical classic "Elements of Geometry (Euclid's Elements)." Matteo Ricci is the biggest fraud and thief in history worldwide, and the Catholic Church must compensate all victims.

45. "Bible," "Jesus," "Jehovah," "God," "Catholicism," and "Christianity" were basically created by the Chinese people.

46. Mathematical, logical, historical, and philosophical proofs of reasoning related to Christianity, etc., which falsifies God, Jesus, Christ, or Jehovah's salvation, and falsifies Greek and Roman history to deceive the public.

47. Methodology for maintaining world health and peace, and improvement in the cultivation of peace fighters

48. The seemingly democratic electoral systems of the West over the past 400 years require fundamental reform, and a 4.0 version of the democratic liberal system for controlling responsible persons.

49. Improvement of Methodology for Maintaining World Health and Peace --- The global consensus and new legal system that need to be redefined for the reconstruction of the world

Keywords: philosophy · world peace · conflict · strategy · civilization · global governance · national governance · metrological historical ethics · global consensus · religion · history · religious ethics · fabricate · Tesla · sustainable development · politics · metrological prisoner of war ethics · FDA · political ethics · Renaissance · Bible · fictional · Sumerian civilization · ancient Egyptian civilization · culture · ancient Greek civilization · ancient Roman civilization · ancient

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Indian civilization · Aristotle · Socrates · Plato · Ptolemy · DaVinci · Euclid · Persian Empire · Shakespeare · the Book of Changes · the I Ching · World War II · political party behavior economy · government behavior economy · state behavior economy · Thucydides Trap · US economic system · the Nile Delta · Egyptian pyramids · tourism behavioral economics · military behavioral economics · universal values · human rights · Native American · Kunyu Wanguo Quantu · equal-field system · socialism · communist system · Tang Dynasty · historical cyclical pattern · social system · Marx · Holocaust atrocities index · Sexual Slavery Atrocity Index · Raped or Gang-Raped Index · ideology · defense behavioral economics · war behavioral economics · International consensus · United Nations conventions · Chaebol · financial oligarch · financial magnate · plutocrat · Huang Chao uprising · financial crisis · economic crisis · Genetically modified foods · Agricultural behavioral economics · Rural Behavioral Economics · tycoon-politician plutocrat · politician · conflict politician · conflict politician · plutocrat politician · war politician · troublemaker politician · troublemaker politician · peace fighter · Methodology · God · Jesus · Christ · Jehovah · Savior · Catholicism · Christianity · Judaism · Eastern Orthodoxy · nuclear weapon · nuclear disarmament · Calendar · Astronomy

Abstract

Since the invention of nuclear weapons, the global quantity has exceeded what is needed to destroy the earth, which is related to the fact that the United States has not disclosed the truth of the psychological warfare of atomic bombs successfully carried out in Japan so far. Key facts indicated that the dropping of atomic bombs on Hiroshima and Nagasaki by the U.S. military was fictional. According to the British scientists' simulation, only 100 nuclear weapons will cause mass casualties and even destroy the entire human civilization. However, this research result is regarded by many as a fallacy. Because they believe that the weather in Hiroshima and Nagasaki returned to normal 2 - 3 weeks after the atomic bomb explosions, and the cities flourished again a few years later, rather than a prolonged nuclear winter. According to calculation of the damage area, the number of nuclear weapons of each nuclear power should be reduced to at least 3-20. According to the calculation of the explosive power, two atomic bombs would cripple at least half of Japan. However, the opposite fact indicates that the U.S. military did not drop real atomic bombs in Hiroshima and Nagasaki, but carried out two nuclear psychological warfare. If the United States continues to conceal the fact that it never dropped atomic bombs on Japan, it will mislead global nuclear weapons policy and seriously affect the formulation of reasonable nuclear disarmament policies around the world. If nuclear disarmament were to occur globally, the saved funds could be used to build at least 100,000 kilometers of high-speed railways. Israel has repeatedly threatened to use nuclear weapons in the Middle East. In reality, even the deployment of a single nuclear weapon in the Middle East will undoubtedly cause significant harm, which seriously threatens human security and world peace. If the United States continues to conceal that the

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atomic bomb drop in Japan was psychological warfare to mislead the world, resulting in Israel's nuclear bombing in the Middle East, the United States will have to bear significant responsibility. At the same time, the United States will lose its global leadership position. Therefore, the United States must immediately consider publicly disclosing the secret of nuclear psychological warfare implemented in Japan during World War II.

40.1 The atomic bombing of Hiroshima and Nagasaki were absolutely fictional

According to scientific facts and logical analysis, the dropping of atomic bombs on Hiroshima and Nagasaki by the US military in 1945 is absolutely fictional. If the US continues to hide the truth, it will only make current nuclear disarmament impossible, and there is no need for the US to continue to hide the truth. Japan is a country of war criminals committed by the entire population. When Japan carried out the Nanjing Massacre and occupied Nanjing, children and women across the country were extremely excited. **The world's most evil Japanese invaders slaughtered at least 500,000 to 65,000 people in Nanjing, at least 650,000 people in the Zhejiang Jiangxi bacterial warfare, at least 51.80-89.60 (100.80) million Chinese people in China, and at least 31.45-54.4 (61.20) million Chinese women were raped and gang raped.**

The evil Japanese plundered huge wealth from China. The evil Japanese looted at least 42,000-63,000 tons of gold worth 5,289-7,933.5 billion US dollars, at least 250 million silver coins, looted at least 20 million cultural relics worth 50,000 billion USD, at least 500,000 kg of natural diamonds worth 132.55-280.5 billion USD, 20 million gemstones such as white jade, sapphire, ruby, and agate worth about 5,000 billion USD, at least 10 million strings of natural pearls worth at least about 800 billion USD, at least 200 million tons of rare earth minerals worth 20,000-30,000 billion USD, at least 49,000 tons of bronze worth about 3,535.71 billion USD.

What is the average investment return rate of these huge wealth in the past 85 years? The worst and most evil Japan in the world has not compensated China and the Chinese people. This is the worst situation in the world formed since the West forged history and established an evil legal system. Have you completely waived the right to compensation if someone killed your entire family, raped your daughter and wife, and plundered all your family's property? If so, please tell the criminals around the world.

Apparently, any funds or wealth used by Japan to sponsor or bribe any politician or military officer are plundered from China. Essentially, the funds or wealth that Japan uses to fund any country in Africa are plundered from China. Essentially, the welfare enjoyed by the Japanese comes from the wealth plundered from China. All the production lines and equipment for the establishment of Toyota Motor, and even all the workers and technicians, are plundered from China.

Japan is a country of war criminals, an extremely evil country where **almost all Japanese people are war criminals and criminals**. Although the evil Japanese have set a historical record by massacring one hundred million Chinese people, resulting in a reduction of 280 million Chinese people, the Japanese strongly hate the US military for fabricating records of killing evil Japanese war criminals in Nagasaki and Hiroshima.

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Many Japanese students were asked about the U.S. dropping atomic bombs, and their idea was to drop them in the U.S. as retaliation.

恐怖炭疽热与日军731细菌战一脉相承(组图)

<http://www.sina.com.cn> 2001年11月30日17:58

101岁高龄的炭疽菌受害幸存者杜樟林。

Fig 40.1A. The rotten legs that still cannot be cured to this day due to the bacterial warfare carried out by the Japanese invaders. **Zhejiang Jiangxi bacterial warfare massacre**

The terrifying anthrax bacterial warfare carried out by the Japanese invaders is in line with the Japanese 731 bacterial warfare (pictured). November 30, 2001. <http://neverforget.sina.com.cn/c/p/2001-11-30/1758476.html>

Fig 40.2A. During the Anti-Japanese War, members of the evil Japanese Unit 731 were conducting bacterial warfare research in China using **live human bodies.**

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[Decades after the Japanese army's germ warfare, this concealed and repeated massacre is still ongoing. 2018-12-12. <https://www.163.com/dy/article/E2RLB20T0514R9P4.html>]

Fig 40.3A. Zhejiang Jiangxi bacterial warfare massacre

The rotten legs that still cannot be cured to this day due to the bacterial warfare carried out by the Japanese invaders.

Victims of Japanese bacterial warfare. Jiang Chungun is an elderly man with rotten feet from Quzhou, Zhejiang. His feet are wrapped in paper shells, and his toes are already ulcerated. He is unwilling to treat his injured foot because he is afraid of being amputated. He said he had a leg cut and would never have a leg in his next life.

[Decades after the Japanese army's germ warfare, this concealed and repeated massacre is still ongoing. 2018-12-12. <https://www.163.com/dy/article/E2RLB20T0514R9P4.html>]

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张丕卿说：从1942年秋天到1943年春天，伪奉天南满医科大学解剖室里先后进行过五次左右的活体解剖。受难人数差不多有25名左右，一次是3人，一次是7人，一次是12人，另外两次都是两三个人。这些被日本人抓去当试验品的都是男性，年龄在三十至四十岁左右。

张丕卿还透露，被日本人当做活体解剖对象的除了中国人，还有朝鲜人1名，德意志人1名，苏俄人5到6名。不过由于当时的试验是在极度机密的情况下进行的，所以作为实验手的张丕卿也不知道那些“实验品”是从哪里弄来的，更不知道他们的姓名、职业、住址等情

Fig 40.4A. Germany was an ally of Japan during the Second World War. The worst and most evil Japanese in the world even performed live dissections on their ally, the German. What did they want to do? Evil Japan is a country and nation that can never be trusted.

At that time, Zhang Piqing, who worked as an experimental assistant in the anatomy laboratory of the Puppet Manchukuo Medical University, said: From the autumn of 1942 to the spring of 1943, about five live dissections were carried out successively in the anatomy laboratory of the Puppet South Manchuria Medical University in Mukden. There were about 25 victims. One time there were 3 people, one time 7 people, one time 12 people, and in the other two times, there were two or three people each. Those seized by the Japanese as test subjects were all men, aged between 30 to 40.

Zhang Piqing also revealed that in addition to the Chinese, there were 1 Korean, 1 German, and 5 to 6 Soviet Russians among those regarded by the Japanese as live dissection subjects. However, since the experiments at that time were carried out in an extremely confidential situation, even Zhang Piqing, as an experimental assistant, did not know where these "experimental subjects" were obtained from, nor did he

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know their names, occupations, addresses, and other circumstances.

Zhang Piqing said: The "experimental subjects" were escorted to the school by the Japanese military police at night. As soon as they arrived at the school, they were sent to the laboratory for dissection. During the dissection, the entire perimeter of the anatomy laboratory was under strict martial law by the Japanese military police.

[亲历者忆日寇活体解剖战俘：头颅锯开大脑取出现场目不忍睹。 **Witnesses recalled the live dissection of prisoners of war by the Japanese invaders: their heads were cut open, their brains removed, and the scene was unbearable to witness.** 2018-05-09. https://www.sohu.com/a/230956093_354075]

Fig 40.5A. The live human experiment carried out by the Japanese invaders. The Japanese commander instructed Unit 731 to carry out the most inhumane atrocities and extreme human experiments. He urgently wanted to understand the human body's ability to withstand them, so that he could build a "copper wall and iron bone" Japanese army with astonishing endurance in the future.

[There is a heated discussion abroad about the Exhibition Hall of Unit 731. Surprisingly, some Japanese netizens have begun to play dumb, and netizens from various countries have launched condemnations one after another. 2024-04-06. <https://baijiahao.baidu.com/s?id=1795567504307025956&wfr=spider&for=pc>]

After the war, Japanese politicians and cabinet members go to pay homage to the Japanese war criminals who died in the sneak attack on Pearl Harbor every year. Kissinger said that if the Third World War breaks out, Japan will attack the United States first. Isn't what Japan is doing a reorganisation of its military forces in an attempt to defeat the United States when there is civil unrest or division in the United States? An evil Japan has not compensated for the crime of massacring the Chinese people and plundering China's wealth to this day. How can the United States stubbornly keep the secret of the success of the psychological warfare of the atomic bombs in the past

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for a country of war criminals? If the United States continues to keep this a secret, it will inevitably lead to the waste of trillions of US dollars in the development of nuclear weapons. It is hard to say that no key personnel in the US Atomic Energy Commission and the US government have been bribed by the Japanese or become Japanese spies and have constantly formulated wrong nuclear weapons policies. If there are no Japanese spies or personnel bribed by the Japanese in the US government and the Atomic Energy Commission, they will surely voluntarily disclose the truth of the atomic bombs in Hiroshima and Nagasaki. **The US FBI should conduct a comprehensive investigation into the relevant US management institutions.**

【摘要】据战时记载，并依据记载推算，浙江、江西等地感染疫病的人数约为230万人，其中死亡约为65万人。日本在中国进行的细菌战，国人受害总人数初步推算约为700万人，死亡约为200万人。

前言：江南之地，鱼米之乡。富足平和的浙江，是中国抗日战争中沦陷时间最早、沦陷范围最广、战争创伤最深的省份。侵华日军曾悍然发动灭绝人性的细菌战，将第一枚炮弹投放在这片土地上，如今70多年过去了，流毒未除，记忆犹在。

作为细菌战全国第一战场，从1939年到1945年，以731部队长官石井四郎为总指挥的日军细菌部队在浙江进行了不少于3次的大型细菌战，造成浙江省、江西省超过230多万人身染疫病，死亡人数超过65万人。

给我一颗菩提

（《浙江在线》援引的一组统计数字中的受害人数更多，该数据显示，日军侵华期间，以731部队长官石井四郎为总指挥的日军细菌部队在浙江进行了不少于3次的大型细菌战，造成浙江省、江西省超过230多万人身染疫病，死亡人数超过65万人，这其中包括1942年前的受害者）

Fig 40.6A. The world's worst and most evil Japan carried out the Zhejiang Jiangxi bacterial warfare massacre in China, resulting in at least 650,000 deaths.

[仅次于南京大屠杀：因为美国轰炸了东京，日本曾用细菌战狠狠报复中国 Because the United States bombed Tokyo, Japan retaliated fiercely against China with bacterial warfare.2017.10.18. <https://www.jianshu.com/p/bc7a9193d647>]

Vice President of the U.S. Harris said in the campaign:

A person who bows to the aggressors and tries to be friends with them will lose the trust of allies and cause the United States to lose its influence. **Such a person is not worthy of being President of the United States.**

Following the same logic:

A person who bows to the aggressors and tries to be friends with them will lose the trust of allies and cause the United States to lose its influence. **Such a person is not worthy of being Statesman of the United States.**

A person who bows to the aggressors and tries to be friends with them will lose the trust of allies and cause the United States to lose its influence. **Such a person is not worthy of being Americans.**

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Fig 40.7A. The evil Japanese military doctor fried a baby in China and prepared to eat it..2023-01-21. <https://www.douyin.com/note/7190872237916867896>

Fig 40.8A. The evil Japanese army slaughtered Chinese babies and used their bones
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to make pipes. 2023-09-18. <https://www.douyin.com/note/7280041787807272227>

Fig 40.9A. Survivor of Bacterial Warfare's Rotten Feet 'Life, Trauma Not Recovered for 70 Years. 2015-05-19. <http://news.sohu.com/20150519/n413309314.shtml>

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Fig 40.10A The evil Japanese invaders skinned a family of three during their invasion of China.2023-09-18. <https://www.douyin.com/note/7280041787807272227>

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Fig 40.11A The evil Japanese 731 biochemical warfare unit performed caesarean sections on Chinese pregnant women, dissected live infants, and soaked them in formalin solution. 2023-09-18.

<https://www.douyin.com/note/7280041787807272227>

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Fig 40.12A. The evil Japanese invaders killed several children with iron nails and wire on a big tree during the Nanjing Massacre. 2023-09-18. <https://www.douyin.com/note/7280041787807272227>

Japanese spies often bribe Chinese people to delete videos and articles reporting their crimes in the media. If the above link cannot be opened, it means that Japanese spies have successfully deleted the article or forced it to be hidden.

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16

Fig 40.13A. The heinous crimes committed by the Japanese invaders.2024-02-14.
<https://www.douyin.com/note/7335482167998319926>

Fig 40.14A. The military dog of the Japanese invaders gnawed at the body of the Chinese people killed by the Japanese invaders.2023-01-31.
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<https://www.douyin.com/note/7194677955715501373>

17

Fig 40.15A. The heinous crimes committed by the Japanese invaders.2024-02-14.

<https://www.douyin.com/note/7335482167998319926>

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Fig 40.16A. Japanese invaders dissected live Chinese babies and placed them in formalin to make specimens. <https://v.kuaishou.com/Ltz3MF>

Japanese spies often bribe Chinese people to delete videos and articles reporting their crimes in the media. If the above link cannot be opened, it means that Japanese spies have successfully deleted the article or forced it to be hidden.

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19

Fig

40.17A. Japanese invaders dissected live Chinese babies and placed them in formalin to make specimens. <https://v.kuaishou.com/Ltz3MF>

Japanese spies often bribe Chinese people to delete videos and articles reporting their crimes in the media. If the above link cannot be opened, it means that Japanese spies have successfully deleted the article or forced it to be hidden.

The United Nations must formulate a convention to prohibit, since 1900, the citizens and their descendants of any war criminal country that invaded a country and massacred one million babies and infants of that country from getting married and having children under the age of 27 within the next 600 years. No matter in which country their descendants are, they must unconditionally abide by this regulation.

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40.18A. Japanese invaders dissected live Chinese babies and placed them in formalin to make specimens. Fig 2023-08-29.
<https://www.douyin.com/note/7272530954965552443>

Japanese spies often bribe Chinese people to delete videos and articles reporting their crimes in the media. If the above link cannot be opened, it means that Japanese spies have successfully deleted the article or forced it to be hidden.

The United Nations must formulate a convention to prohibit, since 1900, the citizens and their descendants of any war criminal country that invaded a country and massacred 10 million babies and infants of that country from getting married and having children under the age of 37 within the next 6,000 years. Once a violation has occurred, the medical insurance and social insurance of the violators will become invalid. For any violation by the criminal country, both the United Nations and the victimized country that has been most severely harmed by the criminal country can simultaneously impose a fine on the criminal country at five times the amount of the violation. If the criminal country fails to pay the fine within one month, both the United Nations and the victimized country can freeze the assets of the criminal

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country or its citizens. No matter in which country their descendants are, they must unconditionally abide by this regulation.

21

Fig 40.19A. During World War II, evil Japanese soldiers commonly ate Chinese heads. The man eating demon - **Nishimura Ichiro**, he ate over a hundred Chinese heads. 2024-04-02. <https://www.douyin.com/video/7353206653325446415>

Japanese spies often bribe Chinese people to delete videos and articles reporting their crimes in the media. If the above link cannot be opened, it means that Japanese spies have successfully deleted the article or forced it to be hidden.

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Fig 40.20 A. People who meet the following 18 criteria in Jinan massacre will be mercilessly killed by evil Japanese people

The Japanese invaders used the immigration strategy to infiltrate some Japanese people into Jinan for living and working, leading to the appalling Jinan Massacre. The world must be highly vigilant about Japan's immigration strategy. They have a thousand years of patience. "The Unified Universe (八紘一宇)" is evidence of this.

Table 40-1A. The Chinese People who meet the following 18 criteria in Jinan massacre will be mercilessly killed by the most evil Japanese around the world

1. Those with flat or student-style hairstyles;
2. Women with short haircuts;
3. Those wearing straw sandals;
4. Those with a belt;
5. Those wearing gray clothing;
6. Those with business cards indicating a Southern origin;
7. Those who are afraid upon seeing them;
8. Those in possession of central banknotes;

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9. Those who open the door slightly late during inspections;
10. Those with self-defense firearms;
11. Those wearing commemorative coins of the founding of the country;
12. Those with military supplies at home;
13. Those wearing leather shoes ;
14. Those with a Southern accent;
15. Those carrying a camera ;
16. Those with gold teeth ;
17. Youth with student-style appearances ;
18. Those with flags or Nationalist Party books at home.

Based on the 18 criteria set by the Japanese for the killings during the Jinan Massacre, should Japan occupy the United States, approximately how many Americans would have to be killed?

Families flying the American flag may all be killed by the Japanese.

Once those who wear leather shoes, have belts, women with short haircuts, those who carry guns for self-defense, or individuals with crew cuts or student hairstyles are killed, it may be possible that the Americans have all been exterminated by the wicked and despicable Japanese.

The strategy of **"the Unified Universe (八紘一宇)"**, aiming for Japanese domination of the world, was formulated a thousand years ago, and astonishingly, they endured for a thousand years for the purpose of harming the Chinese.

40.2. The world's first atomic bomb in New Mexico

At 5:30 a.m. on July 16, 1945, the world's first atomic bomb was detonated in a remote desert area outside Los Alamos, New Mexico. Five days after the explosion, Stafford Warren, the chief medical officer of the Manhattan Project, wrote in a letter to Groves, "There is still a large amount of radioactive dust floating in the air." He warned of **"extremely serious radiation hazards" within a radius of nearly 7,000 square kilometers downwind from the nuclear test site.**

Warren recommended that future atomic bomb test sites should be located no closer than about 240 kilometers (150 miles) from any populated areas.

Residents near the atomic bomb blast site later noticed anomalies - their chickens and dogs died, and their livestock exhibited strange fur and skin conditions.

In Roswell, New Mexico, a healthcare worker discovered a significant increase in infant deaths, with 35 deaths in August of that year. Years later, it was discovered that many of Kent's friends who had attended summer camp with her in 1945 had fallen ill. Kent herself became the only surviving female camper from that year. She underwent thyroid removal surgery and suffered from multiple cancers, including uterine and skin cancer.

She stated that the government "lied," and that she only learned years later that **the "snow" she witnessed was the result of the atomic bomb blast.**

Tina Cordova, a resident of Tularosa Village, New Mexico, saw her family suffer illness and subsequent deaths following the atomic bomb explosion. When she co-

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founded the Tularosa Downwinders, a group advocating for residents affected by nuclear testing, in 2005, she was not aware of the Radiation Exposure Compensation Act.

40.3. The huge waste of nuclear weapons projects by the U.S. and the former USSR

The United States, Russia, and China were originally allies during World War II. It would be common sense for the United States to maintain friendly relations with China and Russia, following the norms of interaction between friends. However, international conglomerates and politicians have exploited ideology to create divisions, leading to antagonism between the two sides. This has given rise to a nuclear arms race that could destroy the Earth.

From 1940 to 1996, the United States spent at least 5.5 trillion dollars on nuclear weapons projects, and even more when factoring in the additional costs. This figure does not include the 320 billion dollars spent on storing and disposing of toxic nuclear waste accumulated over 50 years, as well as the \$200 billion spent on dismantling nuclear weapon systems and handling surplus nuclear materials. When considering all these expenses, the United States has spent over 5.8 trillion dollars on nuclear weapons.

According to a report released by the Stockholm International Peace Research Institute (SIPRI) in January 2016, there are a total of 15,395 nuclear warheads worldwide. Russia has 7,290 nuclear warheads, the United States has 7,000, France has 300, China has 260, the UK has 215, Pakistan has 110 to 130, India has 100 to 120, Israel has 80, and North Korea has 10.

40.4. Nuclear Winter and US Psychological Warfare: Fictitious Hiroshima Atomic Bomb Explosion

A report in the British newspaper The Telegraph said that the construction and development of nuclear weapons by various countries represents a "stupid" waste of funds. Currently, the world has 15,000 nuclear warheads, and the UK has 215. According to simulations by British scientists, only 100 nuclear weapons would be needed to disrupt global ecological stability, trigger a nuclear winter, and lead to the destruction of many people and civilizations around the world.

From the perspective of British scientists, targeting industrial cities or forests with more than 100 nuclear weapons could cause large-scale fires and release a significant amount of radioactive particles into the atmosphere, blocking sunlight, and causing the Earth's surface temperature to drop below 20 degrees Celsius, leading to widespread agricultural disasters, massive casualties, and even the destruction of entire human civilizations. However, many people incorrectly believe that the British scientists' conclusion is entirely wrong. According to the views of the nuclear powers, the idea of 100 nuclear warheads destroying the world is a fallacy. The famous atomic bomb in Hiroshima returned to normal weather within 2-3 weeks, and the city flourished again after a few years. The conclusion that nuclear warheads striking cities would produce large amounts of smoke and dust is not accurate. The erroneous

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conclusions are based on the assumption that the atomic bomb in Hiroshima was a real explosion, when in fact it was a psychological warfare tactic by the U.S. military, and the explosion was entirely fictional. To date, no nuclear weapons have been used in warfare. The reasons are as follows:

1a. Scientists from the United States, China, and Australia used finite element analysis with giant computers to analyze footage of the atomic bomb explosions in New Mexico, Hiroshima, and Nagasaki. Their surprising result was that the three sets of images were of the same atomic bomb, meaning that the footage was shot from different angles of the same explosion, likely to be the one in New Mexico. From a philosophical or logical perspective, **or according to the evaluation standards of the U.S. FDA for process authenticity, this alone can determine that the U.S. falsified information regarding the Hiroshima atomic bomb.**

2a. At the end of 1999, a scientist who participated in the Manhattan Project and a senior U.S. military officer disclosed a surprising history: there was a "Manhattan 2" program, which involved information and psychological warfare.

3a. At the time, Japan had become an isolated island with minimal contact with the outside world, and its communications were fully monitored by the U.S. military. The U.S. military had the capability to control communication and information systems throughout Japan, and could have disseminated a large amount of false information and scare tactics to the Japanese government and people, making it difficult for most Japanese to distinguish truth from propaganda. The U.S. military deliberately selected Hiroshima and Nagasaki because of their distance from Tokyo and limited communication when cut off from the world, making them suitable for information deception.

On August 6, 1945, the U.S. dropped a new type of incendiary bomb on Hiroshima, which ignited a large fire. Then, the U.S. military used electronic interference to cut off Hiroshima's external communications, and impersonated Japanese agencies to send radio messages nationwide, claiming that Hiroshima had been bombed by a massive bomb with great destructive power. Simultaneously, the U.S. military spy network in Japan began working, passing the information to several important Japanese scientists to make them believe it was an atomic bomb.

4a. Before the US military dropped the atomic bomb, it dropped over 60 million leaflets on Japan, which is very abnormal. Typically, in order to achieve tactical effects, a true tactical intention would be hidden, but in this case, the U.S. military deliberately created a false impression of wanting to drop the atomic bomb.

5a. According to historical records, the reason the United States chose to bomb Hiroshima was because it was the most important military port in Japan at the time, responsible for transporting all military supplies (including those to China, the U.S., and all war zones). The most crucial aspect of war was ammunition and weaponry, and Hiroshima was Japan's most important weapons and ammunition storage and production transport port. The United States chose to attack Hiroshima by using heavy bombs and incendiary devices to ignite the explosion of all of Japan's ammunition, and they falsely labeled the enormous power produced as an "atomic bomb."

6a. In photos taken at the center of the Hiroshima atomic bomb explosion, the **The social system that saves humanity – an optimized and improved version of the Equal-Field system of the early Tang Dynasty.**

area around the buildings was flattened, with residual buildings remaining on the flat ground, which contradicts the principles of an atomic bomb explosion. Many of the remaining walls on the flat ground were shattered on both sides, yet the walls remained standing, which is absolutely contradictory to any explosion theory. From philosophical or logical perspectives, or **according to the evaluation standards of the U.S. FDA for process authenticity, this alone suggests that the United States made false claims about the Hiroshima atomic bomb**. The only possibility is that a smaller ammunition depot exploded, leaving the walls of the depot.

7a. The city was leveled, and the strange thing is that there were still standing reinforced concrete walls, even stranger, in the middle of the street areas constructed with reinforced steel, there were orderly tree trunks still preserved intact. The question is, is concrete harder or are tree trunks harder? This is absolutely contradictory to the principles of an atomic bomb or any explosion. From philosophical or logical perspectives, or **according to the FDA's assessment criteria for process authenticity, this alone suggests that the United States made false claims about the Hiroshima atomic bomb. The only interpretation is that it was the explosion of a flat-topped ammunition depot area**. The situation after a normal heavy bomb or small pile of explosives explodes is that the smoke and fire rise upward and when it reaches the top it becomes mushroom-shaped. This can be demonstrated experimentally with a small amount of gunpowder, and this does not match the power image of an alleged atomic bomb explosion and is absolutely untenable in terms of explosion principles. The only possible explanation is that a heavy bomb or incendiary device explosion ignited the explosion in all ammunition depot areas.

8a. After the atomic bomb explosion, traces of radioactive materials from the explosion can certainly be found in the soil around the blast center through analysis for at least 20 years. However, American and German scientists collected soil samples from Hiroshima and Nagasaki after the explosions and found that these soils were almost indistinguishable from normal soil, with no abnormal levels of radiation. Whether from a philosophical or logical perspective, or **according to the evaluation standards of the US FDA for process authenticity, this alone is enough to confirm that the United States was fabricating information. Furthermore, from a philosophical perspective, this is clearly illogical.**

Between 1948 and 1954, scientists monitored almost all pregnancies in Hiroshima and Nagasaki and found no "statistically significant" increase in birth defects. The leader of the Manhattan Project, J Robert Oppenheimer publicly stated after the dropping of the atomic bomb on Hiroshima, "there is every reason to believe that there was no appreciable radioactivity on the ground in Hiroshima." **Based on this alone, according to the FDA's process authenticity assessment rules, it can be judged that the atomic bomb explosions in Hiroshima and Nagasaki was indeed psychological warfare.**

40.4.1. Other logical inferences revealing that the atomic bombings of Hiroshima and Nagasaki were a hoax.

[No Nukes Were Dropped on Hiroshima and Nagasaki. April 21, 2015. <https://tabublog.com/2015/04/21/no-nukes-were-dropped-on-hiroshima-and->

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nagasaki/]

1A. Hiroshima and Nagasaki were not destroyed by atomic bombs 1945. The Japanese towns with their poor inhabitants in their simple wood/paper shanty houses were destroyed and burnt down by US napalm carpet bombings. The rich Japanese lived in the suburbs!

2A. That two atomic bombs exploded in Japan 1945 were just US wartime propaganda (false information) to impress the Soviet union. Stalin wasn't fooled. He (or his deputy Beria) invented/faked his own atomic bomb 1949.

3A. The almost 70 years old hoax from 6 August 1945 is of course still working kept going strong by several governments, crazy generals and plenty physicists incl. Nobel prize winners that cannot get any better jobs than lying for their governments – the only real job many physicists can get apart from being low paid school teachers – and by mainstream media that are experts in publishing false info to brainwash you.

4A. The USA use billions of dollars to maintain the hoax. Russia doesn't spend a rubel or kopek to keep the show going.

5A. The International Atomic Energy Agency, IAEA, and its boss Yukiya Amano and the dictator of North Korea are part of the hoax. Just ask them about it. They are paid to lie about atomic bombs. Just laugh at them and refer them to this web site.

6A. "In Hiroshima I was prepared for radically different sights. But, to my surprise, Hiroshima looked exactly like all the other burned-out cities in Japan. There was a familiar pink blot, about two miles in diameter.

It was dotted with charred trees and telephone poles. Only one of the cities twenty bridges was down. Hiroshima's clusters of modern buildings in the downtown section stood upright. It was obvious that the blast could not have been so powerful as we had been led to believe. It was extensive blast rather than intensive.

I had heard of buildings instantly consumed by unprecedented heat. Yet here I saw the buildings structurally intact, and what is more, topped by undamaged flag poles, lightning rods, painted railings, air raid precaution signs and other comparatively fragile objects. At the T-bridge, the aiming point for the atomic bomb, I looked for the "bald spot" where everything presumably had been vaporized in the twinkling of an eye. It wasn't there or anywhere else.

I could find no traces of unusual phenomena.

What I did see was in substance a replica of Yokohama or Osaka, or the Tokyo suburbs – the familiar residue of an area of wood and brick houses razed by uncontrollable fire. Everywhere I saw the trunks of charred and leafless trees, burned and unburned chunks of wood. The fire had been intense enough to bend and twist steel girders and to melt glass until it ran like lava – just as in other Japanese cities. The concrete buildings nearest to the center of explosion, some only a few blocks from the heart of the atom blast, **showed no structural damage.**

Even cornices, canopies and delicate exterior decorations were intact. Window glass was shattered, of course, but single-panel frames held firm; only window frames of two or more panels were bent and buckled. The blast impact therefore could not

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have been unusual.” **-Major Alexander Seversky**

7A. *The reasons most of these and many more pictures by LIFE photographers on the ground in both Hiroshima and Nagasaki were never published have largely been lost or simply forgotten over the intervening seven decades.*

[First Reports of Nuke Bombing Reported](#)

The first photograph of Japanese victims appeared in Life magazine about two months after the end of the war. [15] But the magazine used a caption to undercut the power of the photos. The caption stated that the photographer “**reported that [the] injuries looked like those he had seen when he photographed men burned at Pearl Harbor.**” [16] For the most part, photographs of the human cost of the atomic bombings seldom appeared in the American media until the 1950s, [17] by which time they would have had little influence on nuclear policy, which had fully absorbed nuclear arms and power into American military planning and civilian life.

8A. If we go back to the pre-Hiroshima nuke propaganda, we find talk of areas being urned into a glass parking lot where no life would be able to grow for the next 500 years. This obviously did not happen! Here are a few photos comparing the aftermath of a firebombing of Tokyo and the aftermath of the nuclear bombing of Hiroshima. Are they very different other than that of the larger Tokyo having more surviving buildings? Is it possible that Hiroshima and Nagasaki were chosen as targets for this deception instead of a more strategic target like Tokyo because they were mainly filled with cheap light paper-thin wooden structures, thereby making the devastation of the firestorm appear more complete?

Tokyo, photo take March 10, 1945 after a firebombing

Hiroshima, photo taken after nuke attack

Should any buildings, bridges and trees have been left standing after a nuclear devastation? Where is this glass parking lot?

Hiroshima aftermath, ground view

Hiroshima aftermath, poles and trees

Well folks it appears another massive lie has been propagated and propagandized into our minds through the mass education/indoctrination system.

Much evidence suggesting that the United States never dropped nuke bombs, (one uranium, one plutonium) is emerging. Watch this short clip from a 1945 newsreel and you cannot see any difference between the U.S. fire carpet bombing 62 cities directly before Hiroshima and Nagasaki.

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Fig 40.21A. Will there still be such good tree trunks and houses left in the central area of the atomic bomb explosion?

Nine Eyewitness Accounts of the Bombings of Hiroshima and Nagasaki. HISTORY | AUGUST 5, 2020. <https://www.smithsonianmag.com/history/nine-harrowing-eyewitness-accounts-bombings-hiroshima-and-nagasaki-180975480/>

The United States should not continue to keep the success of the atomic bomb explosion in Hiroshima a secret. If this information is kept secret, the psychological tactics that were successfully employed during the war should be widely promoted by the United States to the outside world. Instead, it has become a classic case of lies told by American politicians and the military, leading to serious disdain for the United States, its military, its people, and its politicians in the international community.

Most countries mistakenly believe that the atomic bombings of Hiroshima and Nagasaki pose only a low level of harm to humanity, and waste huge amounts of money trying to develop nuclear weapons. **The only prerequisite for saving humanity and the Earth is for the U.S. government to quickly recognize that the atomic bombings of Hiroshima and Nagasaki were merely psychological warfare, and that the U.S. military has never dropped atomic bombs in Japan. Only then can humanity truly believe that the number of nuclear weapons needed to destroy the earth is not too large. Only humans can save themselves.**

It is easy to identify that the dropping of atomic bombs by the U.S. military in Japan as psychological warfare, and only one or two pieces of evidence are needed to make an accurate judgment. If you cannot make an accurate judgment, according to **The social system that saves humanity – an optimized and improved version of the Equal-Field system of the early Tang Dynasty.**

Chairman Mao's definition of a leader, you lack the ability of foresight and you are not suitable to sit in a leadership position and make decisions for the public. If you know the truth but still keep it a secret, it is obviously against ethics and you are even less suitable to hold a leadership position.

Chairman Mao Zedong, a great Chinese philosopher and military strategist, once profoundly pointed out that: **"What is leadership? What is the relationship between leadership and foresight? Foresight is seeing the trend of the future in advance. If there is no foresight, can it be called leadership? I say it cannot be called leadership."** Politicians are typically those who hold leadership positions, and if they lack foresight, these politicians not only fail to create value for the public but also create crises. They must be promptly removed from government institutions and replaced by sober, morally upright, and capable individuals. If anyone voices opposition, the decision-makers must bear legal responsibility and joint economic compensation for any subsequent mistakes. This to some extent limits incompetent individuals from seeking leadership positions and harms the country and the public.

40.5. Japanese politicians plan to use hydrogen bombs to destroy the United States.

According to media reports, during a gathering of the Japanese Liberal Democratic Party, former Prime Minister Koizumi's son shouted, "Destroy America," followed by similar shouts from the attendees. At this high-level party event, Koizumi Junichiro's son, Koizumi Shinjiro, expressed a truth that had been buried in the hearts of the Japanese for 80 years: **Japan wants to destroy America.** Despite his father Koizumi Junichiro, who had served as Prime Minister of Japan, always obeying the U.S. without ever daring to oppose, Koizumi Shinjiro knew that his father harbored hatred in his heart. Therefore, **he boldly shouted, "Destroy America, give them 500 hydrogen bombs."** **Subsequently, other senior Liberal Democratic Party officials echoed this statement.**

Only Americans who have been brainwashed by Japanese people or bribed by Japanese spies will ignore such a serious threat to American security.

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比如现在日本就是这样，在一次日本自民党的高阶政客酒会中，小泉纯一郎的儿子小泉进次郎就说出了实话，也说出了埋藏在日本人心中80年的实话，日本要灭掉美国。

要知道，小泉进次郎的父亲小泉纯一郎曾经担任过日本首相，在此期间他对美国言听计从，从来不敢有任何违背。

Fig 40.22A. <https://www.163.com/dy/article/J3JRQ3T8055369FX.html>

由于父亲担任日本首相，很多话没办法在公开场合说出来，可却有可能在他亲生儿子面前流露出来。

比如说流露出美国对他的压制，而他只能忍辱负重，为了日本的将来不得不卑躬屈膝。而这一切，都被小泉进次郎看在眼里，恨在心中，也就出来了他的这句话。

据说这次聚会中，小泉进次郎高喊，“灭掉美国，赏他500颗氢弹”。而接下来的其他自民党高层也跟着喊出了这句话。

Fig 40.22A. At this gathering, Shinjiro Koizumi shouted, 'Eliminate America and reward him with 500 hydrogen bombs'. And then other high-ranking members of the Liberal Democratic Party also shouted out this sentence.

2024-06-01. <https://www.163.com/dy/article/J3JRQ3T8055369FX.html>

The United States has not made public that the dropping of atomic bombs in Hiroshima and Nagasaki is psychological warfare, which has led to abnormal hatred of the United States in the hearts of the vast majority of Japanese people. They even hope to drop atomic bombs on the United States to retaliate against Americans. However, the world's most evil Japanese massacred at least 40 million Chinese people in just 13 provinces (China has 34 provinces) during their invasion of China, but have yet to receive legal punishment. The world of this era is an evil world.

Some national media also report from time to time that Japan is attempting to use the nuclear material it possesses to build nuclear weapons. Therefore, in any case, the United States should immediately make public the truth that the implementation of the atomic bomb was psychological warfare at that time, publicize the success of The social system that saves humanity – an optimized and improved version of the Equal-Field system of the early Tang Dynasty.

this tactic, and also prompt the world to face up to the research results of British and the US scientists. All countries should destroy nuclear weapons and maintain world peace.

40.6. The Japanese Nobel Prize winner not only acts as the head of spies, but is also warlike. The Japanese Nobel laureate and professor shouted: Japan has long infiltrated China and can still defeat China if a war breaks out.

Last year, the Japanese Nobel Prize winner and professor at Kyoto University, Tasuku Honjo, said: "Even if a war breaks out between China and Japan again, Japan still has the ability and strength to defeat China. Even though China has emerged at present, Japan has infiltrated in many fields and has the strength to disintegrate its interior. We not only affect their future direction; even if no conflict breaks out, I think our influence on them will continue to rise so that Japan can obtain more long-term benefits."

Mr. Nobel established the Nobel Prize with the hope of peace, but it was awarded to Japan, a war criminal country that did not fully compensate for its crimes and victims.

I believe that this university professor is by no means talking nonsense or making casual remarks; a Nobel Prize winner can enumerate infiltration in all aspects of China like counting family treasures and firmly believes that he has mastered our development direction and future.

This is a terrible result of the failure to severely punish war criminals and all the criminals of the Second World War.

You should know that the evil Japanese aggressors slaughtered at least 51.80-89.60 (100.80) million Chinese, raped and gang raped 31.45-54.4 (61.20) million Chinese women, and plundered at least 42,000-63,000 tons of gold worth 5,289-7,933.5 billion US dollars, at least 250 million silver coins, looted at least 20 million cultural relics worth 50,000 billion USD, 500,000 kg of natural diamonds worth 132.55-280.5 billion USD, 20 million gemstones such as white jade, sapphire, ruby, and agate worth about 5,000 billion USD, at least 10 million strings of natural pearls worth at least about 800 billion USD, at least 200 million tons of rare earth minerals worth 20,000-30,000 billion USD, at least 49,000 tons of bronze worth about 3,535.71 billion USD.

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日本教授本庶佑，公开声称有信心从内部瓦解中国！

就在最近，日本京都大学高级研究所有一位名叫本庶佑的特别教授。他威胁说，如果中日战争开始，日本完全有能力打败中国，因为我们已经全面渗透到中国的各个领域，对中国的一举一动了如指掌。我们完全有能力肢解中国内部。

Fig 40.23A. Japanese Professor Motosuke Honjo, a Nobel laureate: Japan has fully penetrated into various fields of China. 2023-11-02. <https://www.163.com/dy/article/IIIU26V10528AOT4.html>

40.7. An Analysis of Military Behavioral Economy in the Mutual Paralysis of the U.S. and Russia

Considering the recommendation of the Chief Medical Officer of the Manhattan Project that no one should be within about 240 kilometers (at least 150 miles) of the site of an atomic bomb explosion, the author calculates the minimum number of atomic bombs needed for mutual paralysis between the United States and Russia, assuming a nuclear weapon explosion similar in power to that of New Mexico. The results show the minimum required number of atomic bombs to be deployed when nuclear radiation covers the entire United States or Russia, based on the premise of both sides engaging in warfare and mutually launching atomic bombs within a bout 240 km radius (at least 150 miles). The calculation results are shown in Table 46.

Table 46 The number of nuclear bombs required by Russia or the U.S to destroy or paralyze each other, respectively

	Land area (million km ²)	The number of nuclear bombs required for mutual paralysis
1	17.098,242 (Russia)	94.54 ≈95

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2	9.834 (USA)	54.34 ≈55
3	Total	150

Annotation: Calculation based on the power of the first atomic bomb.

Table 46-1A The approximate maximum number of nuclear bombs needed to paralyze a country

Country	Approximate area (Km ²)	Calculated value	Maximum number	Actual Quantity
Russia	17.098,242	93.44	94	4,489
USA	9.834 million	53.74	54	3,708
China	9.6340570	52.65	53	410
France	Land area: 672834, mainland area: 553965	3.027-3.677	4	290
the UK	244100	1.33	2	225
India	2.98 million	16.29	17	164
Pakistan	880254	4.81	5	170
North Korea	122762	0.67	1	30
Israel	Actual controlled area : 25740	0.14	1	90
Japan	377972	2.07	3	
			234	9576

★ Calculated in radius of 150 miles

The results show that from the perspective of military behavioral economics or war behavioral economics, the United States would need only 95 nuclear bombs to destroy and paralyze Russia, while Russia would need only 55 nuclear bombs to destroy and paralyze the United States. If both sides were to unleash their anger like uncontrolled boxers and engage in localized strikes, they would need to add a maximum of 5 nuclear bombs each. However, since the first nuclear test in human history with a yield equivalent to 22,000 tons of TNT, the power of nuclear weapons possessed by the United States and Russia far exceeds that of the first test. The number of atomic bombs should be significantly reduced to adhere to the principles of military behavioral economics. However, the reality is quite the opposite. Over the past few decades, the United States and the former Soviet Union have each produced at least 30,000 nuclear bombs. Data from 2016 indicated that both sides still possessed over 7,000 nuclear warheads. As of July 2020, the United States alone had a total of 5,800 nuclear warheads, with reports suggesting that both sides currently possess at least 3,000 nuclear warheads each. However, from the perspective of military behavioral economics or defense behavioral economics, this level of production is pure lunacy and represents a massive waste for the countries involved.

The United States is a corporation controlled by international financiers, and the main forces threatening Russia are international financiers, politicians, and historical enemies. When the United States releases a nuclear bomb on Russia, Russia's nuclear

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bombs will subsequently leave the launch pad. Russia's enemies, such as Britain, Japan, Poland, France, and Germany, may disappear, and the United States will inevitably face multiple nuclear retaliation from Russia. **As a result, the United States and Russia are escalating their attacks on each other, and at this point, there is no need to study military behavioral economics or defense behavioral economics anymore, as nuclear winters will inevitably occur on Earth (The number of nuclear bombs launched by both sides must have exceeded 100.)**. Russia's retaliatory nuclear bombs have already covered the United States, and the international financiers and politicians controlling the United States are basically killed and wiped out. Most people on Earth die directly, and a few die in the agony caused by nuclear radiation. Even if China does not have any nuclear bombs dropped on it, radioactive material on the ground will inevitably be carried and dispersed by the atmosphere everywhere. Like those who did not die, they will inhale radioactive material and eventually die of chronic radiation sickness.

Do both the United States and the former Soviet Union need to possess so many nuclear bombs? Both countries are controlled by a group of lunatics who completely lack economic sense. Many Nobel Prizes in Economics and Peace have been awarded to the United States, but the true economics of the country may be buried among the populace. Judging from the quantity of nuclear bombs produced under US leadership, **the United States lacks serious consideration for military behavioral economics or defense behavioral economics**, hindering global peace and squandering valuable wealth created by humanity. The destructive power of nuclear bombs today far exceeds that of the first nuclear bomb in 1945. However, the primary purpose of nuclear bombs is to sit in weapons arsenals, so the maximum number of nuclear bombs that the United States and Russia should possess should not exceed 5-10 each. In this way, **the United States, Russia, and other nuclear nations could potentially save 10 trillion of USD spent on nuclear weapons**. Having an excess of nuclear weapons serves no meaningful purpose, as no one dares to deploy them first, not to mention the maintenance costs associated with them.

In fact, the maintenance of America's nuclear facilities is not good. Several years ago, in a chance encounter, an American friend mentioned that many people were aware of significant problems with a nuclear device at a certain nuclear facility. If not repaired promptly, a major nuclear accident could occur, inevitably leading to multiple nuclear facility explosions at that location. One or three states in the United States could be paralyzed, and casualties could be difficult to quantify. **Although almost everyone is aware of hazards during a disaster, no one voluntarily proposes corrective action because whoever raises the issue might be held responsible.** Because it is difficult for the author to pay attention to such issues in the United States, the author has never inquired for specific details for many years. In recent years, there have been no reports of a nuclear explosion at a U.S. nuclear base. Maybe someone maintained these nuclear facilities later, or maybe not. However, the author hopes that the American people and the U.S. government can attach importance to the maintenance and security of their own nuclear weapons, and hope to reduce these nuclear weapons even more, like paper tigers.

The United States is an economic powerhouse, **yet such problems exist in its** **The social system that saves humanity – an optimized and improved version of the Equal-Field system of the early Tang Dynasty.**

nuclear facilities. In economically weak countries with poor management, ammunition depot explosions have occurred in the past. If the United States faces an economic crisis, the number of people managing nuclear facilities is likely to decrease, potentially leading to more serious situations. A nuclear base typically holds at least **10-20** strategic nuclear weapons. Once one explodes, a chain reaction of nuclear weapons inside the base is inevitable, possibly resulting in one-third or half of the United States becoming a restricted zone like the Fukushima nuclear power plant. Therefore, the United States should actively and significantly reduce the number of nuclear weapons, rather than making decisions like politicians playing cards. **If the United States wants to reduce the number of nuclear weapons with Russia through card games, regardless, both sides must reduce their nuclear weapons to within 3-20.** Insider sources reveal that Israel has over 300 nuclear warheads, more than China's nuclear arsenal. Israel is not a signatory to nuclear agreements and should destroy all its nuclear warheads.

The data in the table **46-1A** shows that an atomic bomb with the power of 2 to 4 little boys can paralyze Britain and France. The power of modern nuclear bombs is generally ten to several hundred times that of the first nuclear bomb. One can destroy the United Kingdom and France, and a few can destroy the United States. More nuclear weapons are completely useless. The power of modern nuclear bombs is generally ten to several hundred times that of the first nuclear bomb. One can destroy the United Kingdom and France, and a few can destroy the United States. Making more nuclear weapons is completely useless. If humanity does not want to be destroyed, every country should significantly reduce nuclear weapons and eventually abolish them all.

Table **46-1A** shows that the minimum number of nuclear bombs required to paralyze Japan after a nuclear attack is about 3. If two atomic bombs explode in Japan, at least half of Japan will be paralyzed. However, no nuclear pollution was felt in Hiroshima and Nagasaki within 2-3 weeks. According to FDA standards for authenticating the process, it is clear that the atomic bombing of Japan was clearly a successful psychological warfare operation. After about 80 years, the disclosure of this table's data makes any secrecy seem futile. Instead, it benefits Japan, a World War II war criminal country, which wants to portray itself as a victim of a nuclear attack. It is also not conducive to nuclear disarmament, reduction of military expenditures, and normalization of the economies of various countries. Clearly, concealment has led to errors in decision-making, insane production, and huge economic losses for many countries.

Only after the United States publicly declares that the atomic bombs dropped on Hiroshima and Nagasaki, Japan, were nothing more than psychological warfare, can the United States truly significantly reduce the number of nuclear weapons, prevent the lack of maintenance of US nuclear weapons bases, and avoid accidental explosions that turn half of the United States into a nobody's land. Of course, the same goes for the whole world. If that's the case, the global savings can be used to build at least 50,000 km of high-speed railway.

The United Nations and the international community must be aware that, although the Nobel Peace Prize has been awarded for more than 100 years, the social system that saves humanity – an optimized and improved version of the Equal-Field system of the early Tang Dynasty.

current inability to effectively and rapidly control war and nuclear weapons and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of war and nuclear weapons control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.

40.8. The 1950 Korean War between China and the U.S. is likely instigated behind the scenes by chaebols, emperors, and military officers.

The United States has repeatedly used nuclear deterrence against China, the reason being that China, once a wartime ally since World War II, turned into an enemy during the Korean War. **However, in 1950, the behavior of the U.S. military before the Korean War was very strange.** The U.S. military initiated multiple bombings of Chinese territory, leading China to enter the war at the invitation of the North Korean leader.

In August and September 1950, the U.S. military first initiated multiple cross-border bombings of Chinese territory, resulting in many deaths and injuries and the destruction of a street known for its antique trade. The Chinese Premier's protest was ineffective, and China was entirely blameless. If it weren't for the U.S. military's top brass being bought off by international financiers or Japan to provoke war, the military actions of the U.S. crossing the border to bomb China should not have occurred. Even in ancient China, such violations of military orders usually led to execution. Even in the last century, according to China's military discipline, such significant violations would have resulted in severe punishment, likely the death penalty. The top brass of the U.S. military, including MacArthur, were likely bought off by the Japanese emperor or international financiers to intentionally bomb Northeast China, leading to a war with significant casualties on both sides. If the U.S. government is interested, it might consider thoroughly investigating that war again.

If the U.S. military planes mistakenly bombed China, it is unlikely that there would be five batches of planes crossing the border for bombing in one day, especially considering they would have to cross the Yalu River, with the border being evident. These pilots were all veterans of the Second World War, highly experienced.

Subsequently, the U.S. continued bombing. It can be seen from this that, the Korean War between China and the U.S. should have been a war intentionally provoked by the U.S. military against China, likely orchestrated by controlling financiers in the U.S. or the Japanese emperor and officers behind the scenes. **Extracting relevant quantum entanglement information from these financiers and Criminal family--Japanese royal family could confirm this.** If indeed this were the case, and millions died due to the war, Japan, these officer families and financier families would be beneficiaries. The international community should, according to ancient Chinese law or wartime rules, exterminate all these financiers, the Japan emperor, and officers' families. All their relatives within six generations should be prohibited from attending any university for

The social system that saves humanity – an optimized and improved version of the Equal-Field system of the early Tang Dynasty.

3,000 years and barred from engaging in judicial, governmental, military, security, financial, economic, weapons, or biochemical-related work.

Table 47. The Multiple Bombings of China by U.S. Aircraft in 1950 and Questions

	The process of the U.S. military deliberately provoking the U.S.-China War in Korea against China.
1	On August 27, 1950, the U.S. Air Force sent out B-29 heavy bombers, P-51 fighters, and other aircraft, with a total of 5 waves and 13 sorties, to intrude into the airspace over Antong, Linjiang, Ji'an, and other areas in China, conducting bombing and strafing. This resulted in the deaths of 3 Chinese residents, injuring 21 people, and the destruction of five train engines, passenger cars, and guard vehicles, as well as the destruction of two trucks.
2	On August 29, four U.S. military aircraft strafed along the lines of Kuandian Lagushao, the mouth of Changdian River, and Gulouzi, killing 4 fishermen and injuring 7.
3	On September 22, a U.S. B-29 bomber intruded into the airspace of Kuandian Lagushao for reconnaissance, then flew to the skies above Antong, dropping 12 bombs in the Zhen'an Road area, resulting in the deaths of 2 residents, destruction of 28 houses, damage to over 800 roofs and windows, and destruction of 3330 square meters of vegetable fields.
4	<p>The U.S. military aircraft could not have mistakenly bombed China multiple times in a single day with five different waves of aircraft crossing into Chinese airspace, especially having to fly across the Yalu River. The boundary is clear, and these pilots are veterans from World War II with extensive experience. Subsequently, the United States continued to bomb. The Korean War between China and the United States should have been a war deliberately provoked by the U.S. military, likely incited by the financial magnates or Japanese controlling the United States behind the scenes. If it is possible to extract quantum entanglement information related to these financial magnates or Japanese, it could be conclusive evidence. If it turns out to be true, the international community should, in accordance with ancient Chinese laws or wartime rules, exterminate these financial magnates' families or Japan.</p> <p>During the Second World War, Japan committed crimes as a whole. Almost all Japanese people were excited about the Japanese invasion of China and Southeast Asia, which resulted in the killing of at least 51.80-89.60 (100.80) million Chinese people, China's population loss reaches 280 million counting from the first territory occupied by Japan in China in 1894, and the raping and gang raping at least 31.45-54.4 (61.20) million Chinese women. Japan looted at least 42,000-63,000 tons of gold worth 5,289-7,933.5 billion US dollars, at least 250 million silver coins, looted at least 20 million cultural relics worth 50,000 billion USD, 500,000 kg of natural diamonds worth 132.55-280.5 billion USD, 20 million gemstones such as white jade, sapphire, ruby, and agate worth about 5,000 billion USD, at least 10 million strings of natural pearls worth at least about 800 billion USD, at least 200 million tons of rare earth minerals</p>

The social system that saves humanity – an optimized and improved version of the Equal-Field system of the early Tang Dynasty.

worth 20,000-30,000 billion USD, at least 49,000 tons of bronze worth about 3,535.71 billion USD. From 1957 to 2022, Warren Buffett's return on investment: 38,653,482.5%, annual compounded rate: 21.52%; Partner's actual return on investment from 1957 to 2022: 21,390,125.88%, annual compounded rate: 20.44%. From Buffett's investment returns, it can be seen that Japan has obtained unprecedented illegal capital gains using the wealth plundered from China over an average of 85 years in the past. All Toyota's production lines, assets, and workers were plundered and hijacked from China. The vast majority of Japan's wealth today was plundered from China.

Japan had very few innocent civilians; the majority were criminals and war criminals. According to the laws of the Tang and Ming dynasties in China, they should have been executed, and Japan should have been annihilated and should no longer exist. The continued existence of Japan is the greatest insult to human rights and morality, and an insult to the 100 million Chinese and Southeast Asian people who have died. It is the result of the law being tampered with by evil financial magnates. If you or your country believe that the opinions of this writer are incorrect, would you allow people to slaughter your entire family, rape your mother and daughter, or kill 50 million of your people or rape all your women? If you lack empathy, you are not qualified to discuss legal issues.

The "escaped General MacArthur," who abandoned his comrades and had American military leaders eating feces of Japanese in a prisoner of war camp for three years, not only openly accepted sexual bribes during the rule of Japan, but also accepted bribes in the form of gold, with a huge amount involved. If the United States deems it necessary, Americans may attempt to conduct a relevant investigation, and evidence of hidden gold and dollars exists within the family's quantum entanglement information, which cannot be eliminated. In fact, historically, the biggest criminal and war criminal country, Japan, has become the biggest beneficiary for both China and the United States in the Korean War in a very short period of time.

On October 29, 2014, the "PLA Daily" reported that China confirmed a total of 197,653 martyrs who participated in the war to Resist American Aggression and aid Korea. The confirmed martyrs list includes voluntary military personnel, support militia and workers, as well as personnel who sacrificed for the production and construction assistance to the Democratic People's Republic of Korea from the ceasefire until the return of the Chinese People's Volunteer Army.

The Korean War Memorial in Washington, D.C., displays the total casualties, missing, and prisoners of war as follows: a total of 172,847 for the U.S. military, and a total of 2,256,523 for other countries in United Nations forces, with a total of 2,429,370 for United Nations forces. The U.S. military had 54,246 killed, and the United Nations forces killed 628,833. This figure is much higher than the data released by the Associated Press in 1956. Both China and the United States have suffered huge casualties. If the evidence is verified, those responsible for causing the war should be held liable for compensation.

The social system that saves humanity – an optimized and improved version of the Equal-Field system of the early Tang Dynasty.

<p>{Ref. The Emperor of Japan bribed MacArthur, hoping to spare his life, and the amount of the bribe was astonishing. 日本天皇贿赂麦克阿瑟, 只求放过一命, 贿赂金额让人目瞪口呆.2022-03-20. https://www.ixigua.com/7076874969837208072;</p> <p>After Japan's surrender, how much did Emperor Hirohito pay to exonerate himself and bribe MacArthur? 日本投降后, 裕仁天皇为脱罪免死贿赂麦克阿瑟, 付出了多少代价? 2022-08-22. https://www.163.com/dy/article/HFC8UQD90543MD2M.html;</p> <p>Harajiko: The most beautiful actress in Japan, gifted to MacArthur by the Emperor of Japan and unmarried for life. 原节子: 日本最美的女演员, 被日本天皇送给麦克阿瑟, 终生未婚.2022-06-16. https://www.ixigua.com/7109629365058535966};</p> <p>{抗美援朝烈士最新确认人数为 197,653 名 增加支前民工等. The latest confirmed number of martyrs for the Korean War was 19,7653, with an increase in migrant workers supporting the front line. 2014-10-30. https://www.guancha.cn/society/2014_10_30_281095.shtml}</p>

40.9. The way to completely eliminate nuclear weapons and solve the plight of human society today

Today, the predicament of human society is mainly caused by the accumulation after Westerners stole Chinese culture and scientific and technological achievements. In the process of stealing Chinese science and technology and culture, Westerners initially disguised themselves as monks to enter China. In the process of stealing Chinese science and technology and culture, these Westerners got to know some literati who tried to reform the imperial power situation in China at that time. Since astronomy has always been exclusively monopolized by the Chinese imperial family, except for the two major mainstream religions that are officially permitted in China, the emperor prohibited civilians from founding other religions. Some literati hoped to establish **Tianxue (Tian, Tianxue religion, heaven religion)**, Catholicism and Christian religions in the name of Westerners to spread the popularized **Tianxue (Tianxue 天学) thought** and strengthen that civilians could communicate with **heaven (天, Tian)**, like the emperor, trying to bypass the emperor and the government in confusion and establish a new concealed and independent religious system to fulfill their urgent desire to reform the imperial power system of the Ming Dynasty without being discovered and forbidden by the emperor of the Ming Dynasty. However, after these Western thieves of Chinese culture learned the thought of Catholicism, they spread it to Europe and changed the tradition that Europe, France and Russia believed in Tibetan Buddhism in the 17th and 18th centuries. During the spread of Catholicism, Christianity, Protestantism, Judaism and the Orthodox Church were derived and differentiated.

After the Westerners successfully stole Chinese culture, they deliberately destroyed Chinese cultural and scientific and technological achievements and fictitiously made the West as the birthplace of global culture. However, before the 16th century, the West had basically no written language, and the phonetic script in the **The social system that saves humanity – an optimized and improved version of the Equal-Field system of the early Tang Dynasty.**

West was basically created by the Chinese. Cultural thieves did not fully understand the meaning of Chinese in Chinese traditional philosophy (for example, Matteo Ricci did not understand many parts and there were many loopholes when he revised the original Chinese preface to the Bible of mathematical science - **Euclid's Elements**). Westerners could not fully understand Chinese culture and philosophy, resulting in long-term structural defects in Western philosophy. Western philosophy could not guide the morality of Westerners on the right track. Western laws are completely controlled by interest groups, and criminal penalties for crimes that endanger personal safety and society are getting lower and lower. Laws have become a tool for the rich and plutocrats to evade punishment and make profits.

Although a few Chinese literati in modern times created religions in China, such as Catholicism, which gave rise to Christianity, Judaism, Protestantism, and Eastern Orthodoxy, due to the limited level of the founders of Catholicism, the structural defects in the created religions cannot be repaired. When the initiative of the spread of Catholicism shifted from Asia to Europe and was controlled by European missionaries, the ideological system of religion changed, and the structural defects of the derived religions became even more irreparable.

Due to Western aggression against China in modern times and the forced signing of many unequal treaties, Westerners who used to worship China have become extremely arrogant and conceited. The above-mentioned religions have also guided the thoughts of global believers and the public towards extreme selfishness and self-interest, guided countries and regions around the world to create contradictions, guided different ethnic groups in the world to create contradictions, constantly caused internal friction and conflicts, and finally led to wars, enabling Westerners to obtain huge profits in chaos. Western society has continuously created **such a vicious cycle**.

For 400 years, Westerners have lived under false European history, African history, and false Western centralism forged by European missionaries, resulting in the morality and law of the present world having regressed by at least 2000 years. However, the mainstream media in the West today is controlled by Jewish consortia, and the values it disseminates have structural flaws and false democratic and liberal values. This is the value of predatory thinking, but Westerners mistakenly think this is normal value.

Therefore, if humanity wants to completely abolish nuclear weapons, it must first abolish these religions forged by the West in modern times — Catholicism, Christianity, and derived Judaism, Protestantism, and Eastern Orthodoxy, and elevate the thoughts of Western people to a supra-religious level - measuring personal morality with morality. Then, in the country, **the improved and optimized version (4.0, 5.0, 6.0, 7.0, 8.0, 9.0) of the equal-field system of the early Tang Dynasty (Visualized Socialist System)** should be implemented, and an economic model with a stable social and economic structure dominated by state-owned assets and assisted by relatively flexible private capital to build an active market economy should be implemented. Only in this way can conflicts, crises, nuclear weapons and wars be eliminated, the market activated, society stabilized, and the predicament of humanity today be solved.

By the way, if Israel uses mysterious nuclear weapons in the Middle East, Israel

The social system that saves humanity – an optimized and improved version of the Equal-Field system of the early Tang Dynasty.

will also be harmed and Israel will cease to exist. It is hoped that Israel will not be misled by the nuclear psychological warfare of the US military in Japan.

Israel has repeatedly threatened to use nuclear weapons in the Middle East. In reality, even the deployment of a single nuclear weapon in the Middle East will undoubtedly cause significant harm, which seriously threatens human security and world peace. If the United States continues to conceal that the atomic bomb drop in Japan was psychological warfare to mislead the world, resulting in Israel's nuclear bombing in the Middle East, the United States will have to bear significant responsibility. At the same time, the United States will lose its global leadership position. Therefore, the United States must immediately consider publicly disclosing the secret of nuclear psychological warfare implemented in Japan during World War II.

40.10. It is wrong and childish for Western politicians to use ideology to create national opposition in philosophy and history.

When Marx created the classification method of social systems, he overly emphasized ideology, which objectively caused opposition between countries with different systems.

Marx lacked understanding and research on Chinese history and failed to clarify the socialist system, capitalist system, and communist system. China had extremely advanced socialist and even communist ideas as early as the dynasty founded by Wang Mang around 5 A.D. In the middle and late Tang Dynasty of China, the characteristics of monopoly capitalism characterized by the liberalist market economy were very obvious. The financial industry in the Tang Dynasty was very developed and radiated to the surrounding countries of the Silk Road, but the characteristics of privatization, private monopoly or market economy system were very obvious. **It can be said that according to Marx's classification method, the middle and late periods of the Tang Dynasty in China were all capitalist systems.**

From the perspective of historical origin, China's current social system originated from the improved version of the equal-field system in the early Tang Dynasty. It was formed by the Communist Party of China and its leaders based on China's national conditions and practical development, and has the theoretical and practical basis of philosophy and history. Stalin, the supreme leader of the former Soviet Union, clearly pointed out that China's social system did not conform to the socialist system proposed by Marx. China's current socialist system is an original creation in China and is set up to solve the unavoidable historical cycle law that emerged when the equal-field system was implemented in the early Tang Dynasty. In China, public ownership and collective ownership of farmers are implemented for land, and private sale of land and permanent ownership of land is prohibited.

The human social system does not necessarily have to go through capitalist society first before entering socialist society. It may also experience a repeat cycle of the socialist and capitalist system.

The Tang Dynasty system was actually composed of the 1.0 version of the equal-field system. **The social system that saves humanity – an optimized and improved version of the Equal-Field system of the early Tang Dynasty.**

field system in the early Tang Dynasty with the early characteristics of socialism. After experiencing institutional changes and loss of control in the middle period, the entire Tang society gradually entered the 2.0 version of the capitalist monopoly system of crazy mergers and acquisitions characterized by the new liberalist market economy. Finally, due to the large gap between the rich and poor in society and the high concentration of social wealth, **the Huang Chao Uprising (黄巢起义) occurred**. The rebel army killed hundreds of thousands of bureaucrats and plutocrats, eliminating the plutocrats who affected Chinese society and entering a new cycle of selecting talents through examinations and a new land distribution system. In the West, financial crises and economic crises keep emerging, which is also a repeatedly occurring situation formed by the monopoly of private capital based on liberal political and economic thinking. The reason why **the Huang Chao Uprising** has not yet occurred is largely related to the brainwashing of the Western public by the mainstream Western media. However, now the self-media has suddenly erupted, the Western public is gradually awakening, the right to issue currency in the West is monopolized by private plutocrats, and the manipulation of taxes by private institutions will be known to the public. Obviously, Western society based on new liberal political and economic thinking is bound to be unable to solve the dilemma brought about by this system.

Gorbachev once asked the Americans to help design the capitalist system, which resulted in the former Soviet Union's social wealth being concentrated in private hands in a short period of time. In the middle and late periods of the Tang Dynasty in China, there were obvious typical characteristics of a capitalist system society. The financial industry was privatized, free transactions were realized, and mergers and monopolies were free. If Russia or the U.S. hopes that China can help design a freer method and system to concentrate social wealth on a few specific individuals or the rich, it is believed that the Chinese have more historical experience than the Americans. Rich Americans and politicians may provide consultation fees to Chinese companies. The Chinese only found that the free monopoly system in the middle and late periods of the Tang Dynasty in China would only bring disasters, so in the early periods of different dynasties after the Tang Dynasty in China, they tended to a non-liberal monopolistic capitalist system. If politicians, the public, and the media in the United States and around the world think that the improved version of the equal-field system implemented in China is not essentially superior to the liberalist merger and monopoly system in the middle and late periods of the Tang Dynasty in the United States, it should be ignorance of history and the law of historical cycles.

40.11. 144-hour visa free entry, you can come and inspect China and its system at any time

The social systems of China and the United States are the choices of each country. Cultural relics unearthed from cultural sites in many regions of China have shown that China has a history and civilization of at least 8,000 years. The Chinese are the indigenous people of the Americas. China has experienced many changes and historical cycles of the early equal-field system and the liberal political and economic monopoly system after the loss of control of imperial power. The United States has a **The social system that saves humanity – an optimized and improved version of the Equal-Field system of the early Tang Dynasty.**

short history, but has constantly experienced economic and financial crises. The U.S. has the highest GDP in the world and is the richest country in the world, yet it repeatedly forces China to buy U.S. Treasury bonds and lend money to the U.S. every year. Is the US system the most advanced system in the world? Is the US system more advanced than that of China? Is the United States a country with top-level global leadership?

China now has 144-hour visa-free entry for most countries around the world. You can enter China visa-free from most countries in Europe or Asia. If you do not believe that China has an over 8,000-year history, please come and inspect the relevant cultural sites and the current situation in China in person

40.12. How many people in the U.S. government and among civilians have been bribed by Japan or become Japanese spies? They still continue to keep things that should have been made public for the evil criminal country that suppresses the soul and national fortune of the United States.

The evil Japanese built the "**Tower of Suppressing Souls**" or [**the Unified Universe Tower(八纮一宇塔)** tower to suppress the national fortune of the United States and the souls of Americans, as well as the national fortune and souls of many other countries. However, the U.S. government has kept the secret for nearly 80 years that it did not use atomic bombs to bomb Japan during World War II. Instead, Japan sees itself as a victim and is rampant, worshipping the war criminals who launched the attack on Pearl Harbor. Japanese politicians bark that they will **use 500 hydrogen bombs to destroy the United States.** Relevant U.S. departments should review those who continue to keep secrets for the evil criminal country that suppresses the American soul and bring them to the trial stand.

On December 7, 1941, Japan launched a surprise attack on Pearl Harbor, resulting in the deaths of around 2,400 American servicemen and women, with 1,250 people injured. Six military ships were sunk, and 188 aircraft were destroyed. The following day, President Franklin D. Roosevelt declared December 7th as " the National Calamity Day " and declared war on Japan. However, on the 80th anniversary of the successful attack on Pearl Harbor by Japan, 99 Japanese lawmakers collectively paid tribute at the Yasukuni Shrine, which enshrines war criminals from the Pacific War.

An evil and anti-human country using witchcraft and religion to hinder human peace and sustainable development. America is a global leader. How can it closely engage with a country that enjoys killing and is ungrateful, in order to constrain a righteous country like China? How can it become an ally with country that use witchcraft and religion to hinder human peace and sustainable development? Doesn't this harm America's reputation? How can American politicians have such low-level knowledge, morality and strategies?

If Americans ask the U.S. government and the U.S. president why an evil country that has been suppressing the souls and destiny of our nation through religion and sorcery is considered a trustworthy ally and friend of our country, why should we form an alliance with a country that has the highest number of rape and sexual assault cases

The social system that saves humanity – an optimized and improved version of the Equal-Field system of the early Tang Dynasty.

in modern history and has initiated wars against us? What is the moral compass of the United States? How would the U.S. president and government respond?

Fig 40.24 A. The "Tower of Suppressing Souls" or [the Unified Universe Tower(八纎一宇塔) was built by Japan. The "Tower of Suppressing Souls"[the Unified Universe Tower(八纎一宇塔)] still stands in Miyazaki Prefecture, the birthplace of the Japanese Emperor family, suppressing the national fortunes and soul of other countries.

In modern history, the first country built "Tower of Suppressing Souls" to suppress the national fortunes of the United States.

In modern history, it was the first country to build "Tower of Suppressing Souls" to suppress the US soul.

In modern history, it was the first country to build "Tower of Suppressing Souls" to suppress the German soul.

In modern history, the first evil country to obtain German spirit stones in a special way and build a "Tower of Suppressing Souls", attempting to suppress Germany's national fortunes.

In modern history, it was the first country to build "Tower of Suppressing Souls" to suppress the Canadian soul.

In modern history, the first evil country to steal and plunder Korean spirit stones and build a "Tower of Suppressing Souls" in an attempt to suppress Korean souls.

In modern history, the first evil country to steal and plunder Russian spirit stones and build a "Tower of Suppressing Souls", attempting to suppress Russian souls.

In modern history, the first evil country to obtain Peruvian spirit stones in a special way

The social system that saves humanity – an optimized and improved version of the Equal-Field system of the early Tang Dynasty.

and build a "Tower of Suppressing Souls", attempting to **suppress Peruvian national fortunes**

In modern history, the first evil country to obtain Philippine spirit stones in a special way and build a "Tower of Suppressing Souls" in an attempt to **suppress the soul of the Philippines**

In modern history, the first evil country to obtain Singapore's spirit stones in a special way and build a "Tower of Suppressing Souls", attempting to **suppress Singapore's soul**. In modern history, it was the first country to build the "Tower of Suppressing Souls" to suppress the soul of China.

In modern history, it was the first country to build "Tower of Suppressing Souls" to suppress China's national fortunes.

The "Tower of Suppressing Souls" is still established in Miyazaki Prefecture, the birthplace of the Emperor's family in Japan.

In 1957, the name of [the Unified Universe Tower(八纎一宇塔)] Park was changed to Peace Park. In 1965, former Japanese political and military leaders believed that Japan had successfully escaped global scrutiny in the years after the war, and shamelessly restored the name of [the Unified Universe Tower(八纎一宇塔)].

US treasury bond Crisis and the "Tower of Suppressing Souls"?

World Economic Crisis and the "Tower of Suppressing Souls"?

Evil Japanese once set 50 world records for forcing American generals to eat feces

The most fundamental and important thing in formulating reasonable laws is to have empathy. If you think you can formulate laws, but you don't think it's necessary to punish war criminal Japan, you must eat feces for three consecutive years and experience the humiliated life of the American general. Otherwise, you are not qualified to ask for laws to be made according to your thinking. According to the evil practices of the Japanese, you must go hungry for two to three days in a row, and they will give you a basin of feces pulled by the Japanese army, and you must eat it.

The social system that saves humanity – an optimized and improved version of the Equal-Field system of the early Tang Dynasty.

Fig 40.25 A. U.S. general forced to eat feces for three years by evil Japanese
<https://www.163.com/dy/article/E383ATQ90514NI3B.html>

Fig 40.26A. Two generals forced to eat feces for three years by evil Japanese
 [被日军俘虏的将军，每天吃排泄物而活，释放后马上自杀。The general who was captured by the Japanese army lived by eating excrement every day, and immediately committed suicide after being released. 2018-12-17.<https://www.163.com/dy/article/E383ATQ90514NI3B.html>]

The social system that saves humanity – an optimized and improved version of the Equal-Field system of the early Tang Dynasty.

Fig 40.27 A. [被日军俘虏的将军，每天吃排泄物而活，释放后马上自杀. The general who was captured by the Japanese army lived by eating excrement every day, and immediately committed suicide after being released. 2018-12-17. <https://www.163.com/dy/article/E383ATQ90514NI3B.html>]

Table 40.2A. 50 Guinness world records set by U.S. generals forced to eat feces by evil Japanese. (List only 20 records)

1	The first American general who was often forced to eat feces.
2	The first major general of the U.S. Army who was often forced to eat feces.
3	The first U.S. general who is often forced to eat feces, or else he will be punished.
4	The first major general of the U.S. military who is often forced to eat feces, otherwise he will be punished.
5	The first American general who was often forced by evil Japanese to eat feces
6	The first major general of the U.S. Army who was often forced to eat feces by evil Japanese forces.

The social system that saves humanity – an optimized and improved version of the Equal-Field system of the early Tang Dynasty.

7	The first American general who was forced to eat feces by Japanese people for three years.
8	The first major general of the U.S. Army who was forced to eat feces by Japanese people for three years.
9	In World War II, the first American general who was often forced to eat feces by evil Japanese forces.
10	In World War II, the first major general of the U.S. military who was often forced to eat feces by evil Japanese forces.
11	In World War II, the first American general who was often forced to eat feces by evil Japanese, otherwise he would be punished.
12	In World War II, the first major general of the U.S. military who was often forced to eat feces by evil Japanese, otherwise he would be punished.
13	During World War II, the first U.S. military general was forced by the Japanese to eat feces for three years.
14	During World War II, the first major general of the U.S. military was forced by the Japanese to eat feces for three years.
15	In modern history, the first American general who was often forced to eat feces by evil Japanese forces.
16	In modern history, the first major general of the U.S. military who was often forced to eat feces by evil Japanese forces
17	In modern history, the first American general who was often forced by evil Japanese to eat feces, otherwise he would be punished.
18	In modern history, the first major general of the U.S. military who was often forced by evil Japanese to eat feces, otherwise he would be punished.
19	In modern history, the first U.S. military general was forced by the Japanese to eat feces for three years.
20	In modern history, the first major general of the U.S. military was forced by the Japanese to eat feces for three years.

Japan conceals war crimes, and the previous agreements signed with Japan to reduce and exempt war crimes are invalid.

The United Nations must formulate a convention to prohibit, since 1900, the citizens and their descendants of any war criminal country that invaded a country and massacred one million innocent civilians of that country from getting married and having children under the age of 26 within the next 300 years (Unless the victim or their relatives have received sufficient compensation. Unless the victims or their relatives are compensated in accordance with the compensation standard for the 18 victims in the United States involved in this article.). Once a violation has occurred, the medical insurance and social insurance of the violators will become invalid.

All medical insurance and social security information of the criminal country must be made publicly available. For any violation by the criminal country, both the United Nations and the victimized country that has been most severely harmed by the criminal country can simultaneously impose a fine on the criminal country at five

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times the amount of the violation. If the criminal country fails to pay the fine within one month, both the United Nations and the victimized country can freeze the assets of the criminal country or its citizens.

The United Nations must formulate a convention to prohibit, since 1900, the citizens and their descendants of any war criminal country that invaded a country and massacred 5 million innocent civilians of that country from getting married and having children under the age of 31 within the next 1,500 years (Unless the victim or their relatives have received sufficient compensation). Once a violation has occurred, the medical insurance and social insurance of the violators will become invalid.

Fig 40.28 A. President Roosevelt of the United States' evaluation of Japan: "The Japanese are the most despicable and shameless nation I have ever seen in history."

[The evaluations of the Japanese by the world-famous figures.2021-08-16. <https://www.douyin.com/video/6997009958994726178>]

Japan conceals war crimes, and the previous agreements signed with Japan to reduce and exempt war crimes are invalid.

The United Nations must formulate a convention to prohibit, since 1900, the citizens and their descendants of any war criminal country that invaded a country and massacred 10 million innocent civilians of that country from getting married and having children under the age of 36 within the next 3,000 years (Unless the victims

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or their relatives are compensated according to the standard of the 18 victims in the United States involved in this article. Unless the victims or their relatives are compensated in accordance with the compensation standard for the 18 victims in the United States involved in this article.). Once a violation has occurred, the medical insurance and social insurance of the violators will become invalid. No matter what country their descendants are in, they must unconditionally abide by this regulation.

All medical insurance and social security information of the criminal country must be made publicly available. For any violation by the criminal country, both the United Nations and the victimized country that has been most severely harmed by the criminal country can simultaneously impose a fine on the criminal country at five times the amount of the violation. If the criminal country fails to pay the fine within one month, both the United Nations and the victimized country can freeze the assets of the criminal country or its citizens.

Fig 40.29 A.Kissinger: No one can understand the ambition of Japan, an evil nation. Regarding Japan, Former Secretary of State Kissinger wrote a special article for evaluation, among which there are two sentences: "Japan's post-war posture is The social system that saves humanity – an optimized and improved version of the Equal-Field system of the early Tang Dynasty.

often described as a new pacifism, but the truth is much more complicated. The ambition of the Japanese people has a long history, and no strategist has truly understood the ambition of the Japanese people."

[The evaluations of the Japanese by the world-famous figures.2021-08-16.
<https://www.douyin.com/video/6997009958994726178>]

[古今中外对日本的评价意见雷同. Evaluations and opinions of Japan from ancient times to the present, at home and abroad, are similar. April 20th, 2018.

http://k.sina.com.cn/article_6395559593_17d347ea9001005xd3.html]

“日本，這是一個陰險與狡詐的殘忍民族，這個民族非常勢利，其瘋狂嗜血程度类似于歐洲中世紀的吸血鬼德庫拉，你一旦被它看到弱點，喉管立即會被它咬破，毫無生還可能”。

——戴高樂（法蘭西第五共和國首任總統）
头条 @那些段子

Fig 40.30A. "Japan, this is a treacherous and cunning cruel nation, this nation is very mercenary, its crazy bloodthirsty level is similar to vampire Dracula in medieval Europe, once you are seen weak by it, your throat will be bitten immediately, there is no possibility of survival." – Charles de Gaulle (President of the French Fifth Republic)

[The evaluation of Japan by celebrities from various countries: "Every generation has a reason to resist Japan."2023-10-04.

<https://www.douyin.com/note/7285965949507849506>]

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“倭子國，最是反復無常之國。其人，甚卑賤，不知世上有恩誼，祇一味懼于武威……故爾，不得對其有稍許好顏色。”

——康熙（清朝第四位皇帝）

Fig 40.31A. "The Japanese country is the most fickle and changeable. Its people are very humble and do not know the kindness of the world, only fearing the power of the military... Therefore, one cannot show any favorable attitude towards them." - Kangxi (the fourth emperor of the Qing Dynasty)

[The evaluation of Japan by celebrities from various countries: "Every generation has a reason to resist Japan." 2023-10-04. <https://www.douyin.com/note/7285965949507849506>]

Immigrating to China and then creating crises and conflicts, with Japanese invaders sending troops under the pretext of protecting the immigrants, are common means for Japan to wage wars against China or other countries, carry out massacres, rapes, gang rapes and plundering of resources. **The U.S. must be highly vigilant about the immigration policy encouraged by the Japanese government.**

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Fig 40.32A. Japanese officer Haijiu Kusui enjoyed making tobacco pipes from children's leg bones and brutally killed more than 100 Chinese children. After the war, he had a son and a daughter; the son was born with an intellectual disability, and the daughter was paralyzed on one side of her body. [2023-10-26. <https://v.douyin.com/iNmuEEd3/> 1@P.xf wfO:/ 08/04]

Immigrating to China and then creating crises and conflicts, with Japanese invaders sending troops under the pretext of protecting the immigrants, are common means for Japan to wage wars against China or other countries, carry out massacres, rapes, gang rapes and plundering of resources. The U.S. must be highly vigilant about the immigration policy encouraged by the Japanese government.

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Fig 40.33A. [Saving 64 Americans and sacrificing 250,000 Chinese: the most cinematic feat of World War II. February 8, 2018. <https://www.163.com/dy/article/DA44MGF70523GE20.html>]

Why doesn't Hollywood make a blockbuster film about the unprecedented feat of sacrificing 250,000 people to save 64 American pilots?

Why is Japan so despicable, evil, cruel, and vicious? Genes?

Japan must be re-named SRM-Japan or SR-Japan

Which nation is the most evil, cruel, and despicable in the entire universe?

If you believe that heinous crimes and war criminals do not require severe punishment, you should hand over your daughter, wife, mother, and yourself to the criminals to experience the process of being roasted into corpses.

If you lack basic empathy, what qualifications do you have to enact laws to combat crime?

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Fig 40.34A. Alive Mother and daughter were roasted into dry corpses by the Japanese army 731 Unit. 2024-01-15. <https://v.douyin.com/iNmHV65b/> Rxs:/ I@V.lc 03/17

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Table 40.3A. The biggest weakness of the Chinese people is being too kind to evil countries, which is the most serious mistake and criminal offence.

1 3	<p>The biggest weakness of the Chinese people is being too kind to evil countries, which is the most serious mistake and criminal offence.</p>
11	<p>The 7.9 magnitude earthquake in Kanto, Japan</p> <p>On September 1, 1923, a 7.9 magnitude earthquake occurred in the Sagami Bay area of Kanto, Japan. The earthquake quickly spread to Tokyo, Kanagawa, Chiba, Shizuoka, Ibaraki, and other areas, with Tokyo and Yokohama being the hardest hit. According to the Japanese government's statistics, the earthquake caused a total of 99,331 deaths, 43,467 missing persons, 103,733 injuries, 701,627 houses destroyed, and a total of 3.4 million affected people with losses valued at 1 billion US dollars.</p> <p>https://www.163.com/dy/article/HLDGTLPV0553EMF5.html</p>
12	<p>Dongying Massacre: over 700 innocent Chinese workers and businessmen Killed</p> <p>After the Great Kanto Earthquake on September 1, 1923, Japan organized military personnel, police, and the masses to massacre Chinese workers and businessmen living in Japan under the pretext of "maintaining order." More than 700 innocent Chinese workers and businessmen from Wenzhou and Lishui in China's Zhejiang province were killed. Wang Xitian, a leading figure among Chinese workers in Japan who fought against the Japanese authorities to protect the rights of Chinese workers, was secretly assassinated by the Japanese military in September of that year. Thousands of Korean residents in Japan also died in the massacre. In 1924, under pressure from the Chinese government, the Japanese cabinet established a compensation policy for foreign victims, but it was never implemented, and the fact that the Japanese massacred Chinese people during the Great Kanto Earthquake was covered up by subsequent Japanese governments.</p> <p>Newsire Tokyo, September 5, 2022 - On September 4, the 99th anniversary commemoration ceremony for the "Dongying Tragedy" was held in Tokyo, Japan. Participants mourned the more than 700 Chinese laborers and students who were killed in the "Dongying Tragedy" 99 years ago and called on the Japanese government to face up to history and apologize for and compensate the victims.</p> <p>At the memorial service, representatives of the families of the deceased Chinese laborers sent their condolences, mourning the loss of their loved ones. Lin Boyao, an overseas Chinese in Japan, gave a speech and detailed the dark history of the "Ojima Town Incident" during the "Dongying Tragedy" to the audience present.</p> <p>Wang Qi, the descendant of Wang Xitian, the leader of the Chinese</p>

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laborers in Japan who was secretly executed by the Japanese army during the "Dongying Tragedy", emphasized the importance of remembering historical experiences and lessons. He stated that it is not about perpetuating hatred, but about awakening the longing for peace and upholding righteousness in good-hearted individuals. Wang Qi acknowledged the current academic research that has expanded from studying individual cases like Wang Xitian to studying modern China and Japan.

It is reported that Wang Xitian was born in Changchun, Jilin in 1896. In 1922, he organized and established the Society for the Relief of Chinese Laborers in Japan, serving as chairman and engaging in relief work for Chinese laborers, while also fighting against the Japanese government. After the Great Earthquake, Wang Xitian was killed by the Japanese military for his relief work for Chinese laborers and efforts to uncover the truth of the "Dongying Tragedy." He was only 27 years old at the time of his death.

On September 1, 1923, a 7.9 magnitude earthquake, known as the "Great Kanto Earthquake," occurred in Tokyo, Japan, causing over 140,000 deaths and injuries. At that time, during the chaos caused by the earthquake, Japanese militarists incited anti-foreign sentiment and used it as an excuse to indiscriminately massacre Chinese and Korean laborers in Japan. Over 700 Chinese laborers and students, as well as more than 6,000 Korean laborers, were killed in what became known as the "Dongying Tragedy."

[<https://www.163.com/dy/article/HGGN7EHR0514R9L4.html>],
[<https://3w.huanqiu.com/a/c36dc8/4ELY2Gxs3IC>]

Which country in the world is more cruel, despicable, and shameless than Japan?

Which ethnic group in the world is more cruel, despicable, and shameless than the Japanese?

After the news of the Great Kanto Earthquake in Japan reached China, the Chinese people, driven by the spirit of mutual assistance and neighborly love, showed great enthusiasm in providing relief to Japan in response to the disaster. The northern government was the first to take action. On September 2, they sent representatives to express condolences, and on September 3, they held a meeting to discuss providing 200,000 silver yuan in aid to Japan. The first batch of aid supplies departed from Shanghai (via Xinming Steamship) on September 3, becoming the first foreign rescue ship to arrive in Japan.

The southern government began their actions on 3 September. They first sent telegrams of condolences, and then called on the people of the entire country to donate money and goods to help Japan in its relief efforts.

Following this, prominent figures and organizations in the Republic of China,

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such as Liang Qichao, Mei Lanfang, Zhang Xueliang, various chambers of commerce, and the Red Cross Society, all came forward to raise funds and contribute to relief efforts in Japan.

Starting from early September 1923, relief activities unfolded for two months, only ending in late October. **Below are some of the main organizations and individuals that contributed to the relief efforts (based on Mr. Zong Xusheng's "Chinese Aid to the Great Kanto Earthquake in Japan"):**

Duan Qirui Fundraising Association: 440,000 silver yuan;

Beijing business and banking associations: 300,000 silver yuan, 30,000 bags of rice and flour;

Beiyang government: 200,000 silver yuan;

Shanghai Chamber of Commerce: 185,000 silver yuan;

Zhang Zuolin and his son: 10,000 silver yuan, 20,000 bags of flour, 7,000 mattresses, 100 live cows;

Hong Kong General Chamber of Commerce: 100,000 silver yuan;

Red Cross Society: 20,000 silver yuan, 10 crates of medicine, more than 20 personnel sent to Japan for on-site rescue;

Mei Lanfang charity performance: 50,000 silver yuan;

In addition to the above-mentioned documented relief funds, the donations and contributions from various civil organizations, schools, and chambers of commerce cannot be determined, but the total amount is estimated to be no less than 2 million silver yuan.

According to statistics, the total value of Chinese relief materials sent to Japan after the Great Kanto Earthquake reached a staggering 6 million silver yuan (Approximately equivalent to CNY 350 million).

The Chinese people, repaying animosity with kindness, were the first to lend a helping hand after the Great Kanto Earthquake in Japan. Will these acts of kindness and enthusiasm earn Japan's gratitude?

Unfortunately, the kindness of the Chinese people was met with ingratitude from the Japanese.

In a subsequent investigation, it was found that a total of 716 Chinese people were harmed or killed after the Great Kanto Earthquake, among them, 622 were killed on the spot, 11 were missing, and 83 were injured.

The most shocking and lamentable fact is that one of the organizers of the May Fourth Movement, Chinese workers' leader Wang Xitian, was also among the casualties.

When the investigation results spread within the country, it sparked great anger among people from all walks of life, and protests and demands for the perpetrators to be severely punished ensued.

However, the southern government remained silent, and negotiations by the northern government were futile, resulting in no further actions being taken.

At that time, many chambers of commerce and social organizations that had previously donated money and goods were deeply resentful of the previous

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biased actions and withheld further aid to show their remorse.

Japan's Disaster Repays China With

Despite China's kind gestures, Japan has shown no signs of change.

In 1926, the Japanese military formulated the insane "1926 Combat Plan." In this plan, the "war against China" was explicitly proposed for the first time. It outlined the use of seven divisions, accounting for nearly 50% of the total force (16 divisions) for the North China region, including Beijing, Tianjin, and Shandong. This plan, revised over the years, remained in effect until August 1931. (From "War History Series: Army General Staff Headquarters (1)" published by Japan after the war).

From the Kanto Earthquake in 1923 to Japan's surrender on August 15, 1945, Japan committed at least 174 massacres with more than 800 victims each in China.

On May 3, 1928, Japan perpetrated the infamous Jinan Incident, resulting in the massacre of at least 20,000 people. Countless women were raped and subjected to gang rape. The Japanese established 18 murder guidelines and proceeded to gouge out the eyes, nose and ears of 17 diplomats before killing them. This incident set 90 Guinness World Records.

On the evening of June 3, 1928, Japanese spies used friendship and advisory relationships to kill their friend Zhang Zuolin, the Chinese Marshal of the Land and Sea Forces.

Starting from 1929, Japan began pushing for "Manchuria and Mongolia's Separation," advocating the independence of Manchuria and Mongolia to facilitate Japan's occupation of Northeast China as its "historic mission."

On September 18, 1931, the Mukden Incident occurred, with Japan occupying Shenyang and the three northeastern provinces.

Subsequently, Unit 731 established its base in a suburb near Harbin in Northeast China. They built a large-scale bacteriological factory occupying 300 acres of land. Apart from external propaganda, few people knew the true history of this institution. Many might have actually believed it to be an ordinary Japanese military organization. In reality, they were conducting cruel experiments internally. Thousands of doctors, medical doctors, and professors from various universities in Japan participated in Unit 731's biological and bacteriological warfare experiments on living subjects.

In 1936, the Japanese Kwantung Army's Unit 731 forcibly occupied Pingfang Town in Harbin, causing 1,638 Chinese households to be forcibly displaced and left homeless. Many young and able-bodied individuals were conscripted by Unit 731 into labor camps where they suffered abuse. They witnessed the numerous atrocities committed by the Japanese Unit 731 against the Chinese people, and the testimonies of the survivors have brought this painful history back into focus.

Unit 731 imposed regulations on surrounding villages, stating that households

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with males aged 18 to 55 must serve at least four months per year. Families with three or more males must have one person forced into a year-long labor service. For all laborers under Unit 731, no human rights were given, and their management was cruel, completely disregarding their well-being, let alone any dignity.

One of the tortures inflicted by Unit 731 was "feces punishment." According to survivor testimonies: "Once, a young Chinese laborer thought that nobody was watching and tried to lift the cover of a loaded truck to see what was inside. However, the guards discovered him and took him to the guardhouse. The arrested laborer begged to explain that he was just curious and not a spy, but the Japanese guards ignored him. They bound his limbs with wire and threw him into a huge pit of excrement in the guardhouse. The laborer was soaked in feces and urine, crying desperately, while the Japanese cruelly defecated and urinated over his head. After enduring nearly a month of agony, this young man was sent to prison and eventually killed as an experimental subject."

Another torture method was the "cot punishment." In the torture chamber in Unit 731 compound, there was a wooden bed with iron rings installed on both sides at the corresponding positions of the person's hands and feet. The "prisoner" would lie on the bed with their face upwards, and their hands and feet would be fixed with iron rings. Then, they would be tied to the bed with ropes, and their heads would be placed in a wooden box at the position of the pillow, securing their entire head. The interrogator would splash water on the "prisoner's" face from a bucket, and the water in the wooden box would gradually increase. When the water level exceeded their nose, the "prisoner" would inhale the water along with air, choking severely. The interrogator would then pour water into the box repeatedly, causing the "prisoner" to suffer from severe choking and gradually lose consciousness. The Japanese would then pull the "prisoner" off the bed to revive them. This method subjected Chinese laborers to extreme pain. However, the cunning Japanese never caused physical harm to the "prisoner" or hindered their ability to continue working. Workers experienced pain and fear but were ultimately forced to comply.

There was also the "nail boot punishment." One older Chinese laborer named Xing, who had a stutter, was brutally beaten by Japanese guards when he could not respond fluently to their questions. He was then forced to wear boots with iron nails for labor.

Dragging his feet, covered in blood, the stench of blood mixed with the heavy smell of disinfectant in the "factory" seemed to sound an alarm to everyone. However, each time the Japanese guards passed by, they always wore a smile of victory.

The Japanese invaders also invented over 500 types of torture, including "four cornered oxen", "sex slave chairs", water houses, electric shocks, pencil fingers, and more.

Which country in the world is more cruel, despicable, and shameless than

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Japan?

Which ethnic group in the world is more cruel, despicable, and shameless than the Japanese?

Japanese destroyed most of the buildings and destroyed evidence

On August 15, 1945, Emperor Hirohito of Japan announced the unconditional surrender and signed a ceasefire agreement. Unit 731 was also immediately disbanded. As the members of the 731 Unit fled, they destroyed most of the buildings and destroyed evidence. Not only were all the prisoners of war held here executed at that time, but the Japanese also set fire to their bodies, related documents, and buildings.

The location of the 731 Unit's invasion site in Japan is the largest research, experimentation, and production base for bacterial weapons in world history. It was the headquarters where Japanese militarism violated international conventions and conducted frostbite, bacterial infection, and gas experiments on live humans. It is an important piece of evidence of Japan's external aggression, resource plundering, and trampling on China's sovereignty.

Although Japan surrendered unconditionally after the end of World War II, the 731 Unit still continued to exist in a different form. When the United States took over Japan, the experimental personnel of Unit 731 handed over all their research findings to the Americans. In addition, Shiro Ishii joined a secret laboratory base called Detrick, established by the United States. These Japanese and Americans continued to conduct secretive and inhumane experiments there.

Of course, experimental data of the 731 Unit were not only possessed by the United States. After the Soviet Army defeated the Kwantung Army of Japan, they also captured many members of Unit 731. Through interrogation and questioning, they also obtained some of the experimental data.

What is most infuriating is that these demons who committed heinous crimes were able to escape punishment after the war because they had access to a large amount of human experimentation data, which was secretly manipulated. The leaders of these devils fled overseas to continue their evil deeds, while the lower-ranked members returned to their home country and became well-known figures in their respective industries, wearing masks and pretending as if they had never felt an ounce of guilt or remorse.

Waiting for the opportunity to attack the United States' biological warfare

A secret handwritten order by Shiro Ishii, written in a large notebook, detailed Unit 731's actions during the period from August 16 to 27, 1945, the day after the Japanese Emperor announced the surrender. Shiro Ishii ordered, "As the American forces will land near Tokyo in Sagami Bay on August 25th, we must distribute biological weapons throughout Japan before they arrive and launch a comprehensive biological war against the invading American forces." Shiro Ishii also detailed three weapons to be used for biological war against U.S. forces - "Chinese logs," "Manchurian PX," and "Japanese beauties." The term

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"Chinese logs" refers to Chinese victims carrying disease-causing bacteria. According to testimonies from former members of Unit 731, all "logs" were killed by Unit 731 before retreating. However, it is now believed that Unit 731 secretly transported some Chinese victims back to Japan and silenced them after the conspiracy was exposed. "Manchurian PX" refers to fleas contaminated with bacteria. This weapon was provided by the Fourth Division of Unit 731. The Fourth Division was a "large-scale biological weapon manufacturing factory" capable of mass-producing plague, typhoid fever, anthrax, and cholera bacteria.

The "Japanese beauties" were Japanese women who volunteered to act as carriers of bacteria and had "sexual contact" with senior U.S. military officers to achieve a surprise attack effect. On August 26, 1945, two days before the advanced team of U.S. troops landed in Japan, after the high-level Japanese military learned of Unit 731's plan, they issued several stern orders to Unit 731: "Do not sacrifice without purpose." **"Wait for the right moment."** These instructions came from the Chief of the General Staff and the Deputy Chief of the General Staff of the Japanese military.

Japanese scholars believe that the ultimate reason for the highest level of the Imperial Japanese Army's decision to halt the extreme actions of Unit 731 was to save the lives of the Japanese people and avoid the risk of "extinction". Although Unit 731 possessed some "antidotes" for their biological weapons, the war had already completely destroyed Japan's domestic epidemic prevention system and pharmaceutical production capacity. If the biological weapons were to be deployed in the Japanese archipelago, it could potentially lead to the destruction of the Japanese nation. Additionally, there were concerns about retaliation from the US military. The atomic bombs dropped on Hiroshima and Nagasaki had completely shattered the will of the Japanese soldiers. If Unit 731 succeeded in causing significant casualties to the US military with their biological weapons, it would not be ruled out that the US military might retaliate against Japan again with atomic bombs, which would ultimately result in the potential "extinction" of the Yamato people.

Japan Unit 731 conducted live dissections on tens of thousands of Chinese people and Allied prisoners of war (fixing the victims to the operating table without any anesthesia, dissecting them while fully conscious, and removing their organs, with the victims screaming until their last breath), as well as live dissections of children without anesthesia (after anesthetizing boys from head to toe, the medical doctors and professors of Unit 731 took out their intestines, pancreas, liver, kidneys, stomach, and other internal organs, then removed their skulls, and finally took out their brains, leaving their bodies nothing more than empty shells).

In addition to experiments on pregnant women and the removal of infants, Unit 731 also conducted a **"Motherly Love" experiment** (Japanese medical doctors and professors from Unit 731 observed different ethnic mothers and their infant children together in a room, continuously heating up the room to

see if the mother used the child as a footstool or chose to pick up the child. This experiment, devoid of humanity, was done in the name of motherly love, truly ironic and ludicrous).

Dry Experiment (Japanese doctors, nurses, and professors lock people in a closed laboratory and tie them to chairs. The subjects are continuously blown with high heat until they are slowly roasted to death. The criterion is that the subject's sweat cannot drop to the floor. The goal is to completely dehydrate the subject and turn them into a mummy, **as human bodies consist of 78% water**).

The subjects of these experiments included Russians, Chinese, Mongolians, Koreans, and prisoners of war from the Allied forces.

Starvation Experiment (Japanese doctors, nurses, and professors only provide water to the victims to see how long they can survive on water alone. The longest recorded survival time is around 60 days).

Pressure Experiment (People are locked in a sealed laboratory, and the air inside is continuously pumped out. Victims experience extreme headaches and sudden eye pressure increase, eventually causing the eyeballs to pop out of the eye sockets. Internal organs may explode or fly out through the anus, causing extreme pain.)

Thirst Experiment (Victims are only given bread to eat and are deprived of water. They die while vomiting blood.)

Gassing Experiment (Poison Gas Experiment):

Japanese Unit 731 Mother and Child Gas Experiment (In order to test the effects of a new type of gas, Japanese doctors, nurses, and professors lock a young mother and daughter inside a gas chamber. The young girl stares wide-eyed as the gas enters, and the mother immediately covers her daughter's mouth and nose, trying to minimize her exposure to the gas. However, they still die in the end.)

Flamethrower Experiment (In the summer of 1943, there were over a dozen scrapped tanks and armored vehicles at the experimental field of Unit 731. Soon, a group of Maruta, dressed in military green uniforms, handcuffed and shackled, were dragged in front of the tanks and armored vehicles. One by one, they were untied and, under the threat of machine guns and whips, pushed into the narrow entrance of the tanks, which were then sealed shut. Inside the tanks and armored vehicles, under the scorching sun of summer, it was as hot as a steam bath. Once all the personnel were forced inside, soldiers of the Kwantung Army, armed with flamethrowers, stood at distances of 10, 20, and 30 meters away from the tanks, aiming the nozzles of the flamethrowers at them. White flames, reaching temperatures of up to 1000 °C, surrounded the armored vehicles and tanks with Maruta, creating a deafening roar and accompanied by small explosions. Only 20 seconds had passed, but for the personnel present, it might as well have been a century. When the thick smoke of red and black dissipated, burnt vehicles could be seen. The tanks were on fire, and the tracks and armor plates had warped due to the high temperature. Initially, noises of banging and intermittent cries for help could still be heard from inside the tanks,

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but as minutes and hours passed by, the high residual heat naturally dissipated, and all sounds had long disappeared. The Japanese soldiers began inspecting the interiors of the vehicles. The Maruta inside the tanks and armored vehicles had already been burned to a crisp, curling up in the center of the tanks, as far away from the flames as possible. Due to the intense heat, the Maruta had charred. The camera crew had captured the scenes of each vehicle. Most of this damning evidence had been destroyed after Japan's defeat in the war, and we can only rely on the testimonies of Unit 731 personnel to understand the various atrocities committed by the Japanese army during that time.

Plague Experiment: Japanese doctors, nurses, and professors injected plague bacteria directly into the subjects' bodies and observed their physical reactions. Through this experiment, the Japanese created biological agents and bacterial bombs. The plague bacterium is a virus with a mortality rate of over 75% when infected; the biological agents are synthetic industrial toxins similar to the current herbicide, causing death or disability when entered into the human body.

Tooth Extraction without Anesthesia: Japanese doctors, nurses, and professors aimed to test whether casualties could endure tooth extraction surgery without anesthesia, and the experiment results showed that no one could endure it.

"Manchuria" PX Experiment refers to human experiments using infected fleas. The weapon was provided by Unit 731, Fourth Department. The Fourth Department was a "large-scale biological warfare weapons factory" capable of mass-producing plague, typhoid bacteria, anthrax, and cholera.

Human and Horse Blood Exchange: The purpose of the experiment was to determine how to quickly transfuse heavily bleeding casualties on the battlefield. During the experiment, half of the subject's blood was withdrawn, causing the body to involuntarily go into convulsions due to excessive blood loss. Several doctors in the laboratory would then forcefully restrain the subject's limbs and immediately infuse animal blood (mostly horse blood) into the subject, observing their final reaction. The reality, however, was extremely cruel, as none of the subjects were able to survive the immune response, and their fate was only death.

Experiment on Limb Exchange in the Human Body (This experiment sounds extremely cruel even just by its name. Japanese doctors, nurses, and professors conducted the experiment using two healthy individuals. Firstly, the two individuals were bound together, and then their limbs were amputated. After that, the limbs were exchanged and reattached to the individuals. This experiment would have had special significance in restoring combat effectiveness for disabled soldiers in the Japanese military. However, due to rejection phenomena and the limited medical technology at the time, the experiment ultimately ended in failure. The experimenters themselves did not receive effective medical treatment from the Japanese military and eventually died from infections. Those who did not die were cruelly killed by the Japanese.)

Experiment on Human and Animal Hybridization (Japanese doctors, nurses,

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and professors, in order to research ways to optimize so-called "inferior races," implemented inhumane methods of human and animal hybridization in Unit 731. They forced women to mate with horses or wolves, and those who resisted would undergo even more horrific experiments. Japanese soldiers even openly abducted women from the streets and threw them into secret prisons, subjecting them to inhumane experiments on human and animal hybridization in Unit 731, which caused numerous compatriots to be humiliated and killed.)

Blood Injection into Seawater Experiment

Doctors, nurses, and professors in Japan inject seawater into test subjects to test whether seawater can substitute for saline solution. Injection of seawater has been proven to be fatal. Experimenters continue to test with different substances, such as animal fluids.

Thrombosis Induction Experiment: In order to induce thrombosis, doctors, nurses, and professors in Japan even inject air into some test subjects' bodies for research purposes.

Forced Infection with Syphilis and Live Dissection Experiment

Because syphilis was a major problem in the Japanese army, women were subjected to forced experiments in order to study how to mitigate the effects of this disease. After a prisoner became infected with syphilis, doctors, nurses, and professors in Japan forced them to have sexual intercourse with an uninfected prisoner in order to study how syphilis spreads. As the infections occurred, the victims were dissected while still alive.

Inversion Experiment: The test subjects were made to stand upside down to see how long they could endure.

Death by Crushing Experiment: Doctors, nurses, and professors in Japan placed heavy objects on test subjects to see how much weight would crush an average person to death.

Centrifuge Centrifugal Experiment: Test subjects were placed in giant centrifuges to test the effects of centrifugal force on the human body, similar to the gravity training pilots and astronauts undergo. Japanese doctors, nurses, and professors conducted a series of tests on the victims, with the magnitude of the rotation force increasing until it claimed their lives.

X-ray Irradiation Experiment: Doctors, nurses, and professors in Japan subjected test subjects to lethal doses of X-ray irradiation to test different levels of radiation on the human body and investigate the long-term effects of radiation exposure. Each case resulted in fatality.

The live person frying experiment of the Japanese 731 unit

The Japanese put their babies in a hot oil pot, and the more they struggled and struggled, the happier they laughed beside them, which was outrageous.

Boil to death experiment in boiling water

Put the experimenter in boiling water and boil them alive to death

Japanese medical professionals involved in inhumane human experiments or biological warfare with bacteria come from various

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institutions including the University of Tokyo, Tokyo University of Fisheries, Kyoto University (formerly known as "Kyoto Imperial University" before World War II), Hokkaido University, Osaka University, Osaka City University Medical School, Okayama University, Showa Pharmaceutical University, National Defence Academy, Nagoya City University, Kanazawa University, Mie University, Self-Defense Force Health School, Mie Prefectural Medical School, National Institute of Infectious Diseases of Japan, Tokyo Metropolitan Institute of Public Health, Japan Public Health Institute, Nagoya Public Health Institute, Kitasato Institute, Kyoto Microbiology Research Institute, Ministry of Education officials, Western hospitals, Noguchi Maternity and Gynecological Hospital, Hifuji Hospital, Eguchi Hospital, Kodama Hospital, Kamo Hospital, Hojo Hospital, Takahashi Hospital, Japanese Pharmaceutical, Japan Green Cross Corporation, Japan Green Cross Corporation Tokyo Branch, Japan KENWOOD Corporation, Takeda Pharmaceutical Research of Japan, Xinghe Pharmaceutical Tokyo Research Institute, and various experts in the medical field.

The Nanjing Massacre, which began in December 1938, and according to Japanese records, the population of Nanjing decreased by 785,000 within two and a half months before and after the massacre. Japanese invaders killed **at least 500,000-650,000 Chinese and rape 200,000 women**, as well as looting at least **6,000 tons of gold** from the government.

42 Days of Nanjing Massacre

At least **500,000** Chinese killed by evil, brutal and anti-human Japanese invaders (Another article will derive this result).

Singapore Massacre: At least **170,000** Chinese killed by evil, brutal and anti-human Japanese invaders.

Southeast Asian Chinese Massacre: Overseas Chinese killed **at least 500,000** by evil Japanese invaders

at least 5,000 households have disappeared, at least 100,000 women have been raped, at least 10,000 tons of gold, 10,000 tons of silver, 100 tons of natural diamonds, 10 million pieces of jewelry have been looted, and at least \$100-300 million has been extorted. A large number of factories and equipment were destroyed or looted to Japan.

Evil Japanese invaders massacre in Taiwan: **650,000 Victim**

Typical bacterial biological warfare in China

Bacterial massacre along railways and highways in North China in August 1938

In just one month in August, the number of **civilian deaths** has reached **40,000 to 50,000.**

According to the Xinmin Daily on September 22, 1938, the Japanese army

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scattered a large number of bacteria such as cholera and typhoid fever etc. in drinking wells in important villages and towns along railways and highways in North China, causing the epidemic to become rampant. In one month of August, the number of civilian deaths reached 40,000 to 50,000.

Huabei Bacterial Massacre(Bacterial Massacre in North China) : Evil Japanese in North China: Bacteriological Warfare Massacre

At least 270,000 civilians killed(excluding military deaths), over 12 million people infected

Kaikou Town Bacteriological Massacre in Yueyang: over 10,000 people died
Yueyang Bacteriological Chemical Massacre:

464,109 casualties in the five counties of Yueyang, with 159,560 deaths.

Change pestis Bacterial slaughter:

In the early morning of November 4, 1941, the 731 unit of the Japanese invaders dropped 36 kg of virulent infectious pestis bacteria on the Ji'e Lane, Guanmiao Street, Change City, causing a pestis pandemic in Change City and the surrounding rural counties for more than five years. Between 1941 and 1942, the number of deaths in urban and rural areas of Change was at least 15,000 or more.

Yunnan Bacterial Warfare Massacre launched by the world's most evil Japanese

In 1942, the seemingly polite but extremely evil, extremely despicable, extremely savage, fond of stealing and looting, and extremely anti-human Japanese launched a large-scale Bacterial Warfare Massacre in Yunnan, resulting in the death of at least 200,000-300,000 Chinese people. The exact number of victims is difficult to determine.

Lu Xi Bacterial Warfare Massacre launched by the world's most evil Japanese

During the Lu Xi Bacterial Warfare Massacre carried out by the seemingly polite but extremely evil, extremely despicable, extremely savage, fond of stealing and looting, and extremely anti-human Japanese, they killed at least 500,000 – 600,000 Chinese people, created a deserted area spanning 1,500 kilometers, and 24 counties becoming uninhabited areas.

Qu County Bacterial Warfare Massacre launched by the world's most the seemingly polite but extremely evil, extremely despicable, extremely savage, fond of stealing and looting, and extremely anti-human Japanese

From 1940 to 1948, there were a total of over 300,000 cases and over 50,000 deaths.

Guangzhou Bacterial and Biochemical Massacre launched the world's most

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seemingly polite but extremely evil, extremely despicable, extremely savage, fond of stealing and looting, and extremely anti-human Japanese

At least **100,000 - 300,000 Cantonese** died tragically from 1938 to 1945

Bacterial Massacre in Coastal Counties of Guangdong Province

At least 1 million deaths in various coastal counties.

Pestis Massacre in Eastern Inner Mongolia in August 1945

From 1945 to 1948, the most seemingly polite but extremely evil, extremely despicable, extremely savage, fond of stealing and looting, and extremely anti-human Japanese in the world launched the pestis massacre, a total of 47,522 cases and **39,097 deaths** occurred in the eastern region of Inner Mongolia, affecting 18 counties.

Pestis Massacre in Fujian: At least 75,000 deaths

Zhejiang-Jiangxi Bacterial Warfare Massacre

The Zhejiang-Jiangxi Bacterial Warfare Massacre perpetrated by world's most seemingly polite but extremely evil, extremely despicable, extremely savage, fond of stealing and looting, and extremely anti-human Japanese resulted in the **death of about 650,000 Chinese people.**

Cholera in the three northeastern provinces:

At least 50,000 deaths

On August 29, 1938, a cholera epidemic broke out in Chenzhou, Hunan Province, with a large number of deaths. This epidemic was caused by the Japanese invading army bombing Chenzhou and releasing bacteria. In 1946, another epidemic broke out in Chenzhou, resulting in numerous deaths.

The bacterial warfare launched by the evil Japanese resulted in the deaths of at least 2.75 million Chinese people and affected over 30 million in China.

If European or American bloggers make short videos of Japan's massacre of bacterial warfare in China, the video's viewership may well exceed one or ten million, attracting many fans.

Ryukyu Massacre: Japanese invaders **killed at least 360,000** indigenous people in Ryukyu.

The seemingly polite but extremely evil, extremely despicable, extremely savage, fond of stealing and looting, and extremely anti-human Japanese carried out **large-scale massacres killing over a thousand people at least 154 times** in China, and the number of killings below a scale of 1,000 is **incalculable.**

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It is necessary to be vigilant that: forgetting history means betrayal. If, currently or in the future, Japanese or Japanese descendants control or hold a majority shares in a city's water supply or water treatment plant, a conflict could lead the city into a bacterial or biological war crisis, resulting in mass and rapid casualties. In particular, cities with large numbers of Japanese immigrants could face a major disaster, as seen in the Nanjing Massacre and the Shanghai Incident, both caused by Japanese immigrants.

Japan has issued counterfeit currency worth 4 billion yuan in China, looted 42,000 tons of gold worth **5,289 billion US dollars**, at least 250 million silver coins, looted 20 million cultural relics worth 50,000 billion US dollars, 500,000 kg of natural diamonds worth **132.55-280.5 billion** US dollars, 20 million gemstones such as white jade, sapphire, ruby, and agate worth about **5,000 billion US dollars**, at least 10 million strings of natural pearls worth at least about 800 billion US dollars, at least 200 million tons of rare earth minerals worth **20,000-30,000 billion US dollars**, at least 49,000 tons of bronze worth about **3,535.71 billion US dollars**, at least 1.06 billion tons of coal worth 114.4 billion US dollars, at least 700 million cubic meters of wood worth 420 billion US dollars, **at least 800 million tons of food worth about 700 billion US dollars**, at least 1,000 tons of platinum worth about 32.258-37.868 billion US dollars, at least 20 million tons of cotton worth about 53.3 billion US dollars, at least 180 million tons of iron ore worth about 18-23.4 billion US dollars, at least 100 million tons of salt worth about 42 billion US dollars, as well as 480 million pigs, sheep, chickens, and ducks, and 20 million head of cattle, horses, and donkeys. Additionally, 300 million houses were destroyed. These looted assets have accumulated significant wealth for Japan's development over an average of 85 years and must be compensated with a minimum of 5% compound interest. Otherwise, any country has no reason not to kill the evil Japanese and recover these assets.

[The Japanese bacterial warfare that resulted in the death of 500,000 people in Luxi. April 3, 2022.

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Which country in the world is more cruel, despicable, and shameless than

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	<p>Japan?</p> <p>Which ethnic group in the world is more cruel, despicable, and shameless than the Japanese?</p>
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In Chinese society, no family members of the victims in China have signed an agreement with the government not to demand that evil Japan compensate for the crimes of massacre, rape, gang rape and plundering committed by the Japanese invaders against the Chinese during the Japanese invasion of China. If there are a few, they can be removed from the list of claimants. If not, claims will be made based on the number of massacres by the Japanese invaders and the number of injuries to the Chinese, and claims will be made according to the property looted and destroyed. All supporters of the claim around the world can share the compensation payment.

If the United States hopes to solve the national debt crisis, help the victims in China to claim compensation from Japan, and force Japan to release the wealth plundered from China, the United States will quickly extricate itself from the financial crisis. All individuals, institutions and countries involved in the claim can obtain very good returns.

40.13. Is it politically correct for Americans to ally with evil aggressors?

Table 40.4A. The logical deduction of whether it is correct for the United States to continue to keep secrets for the evil aggressor

1	Vice President of the U.S. Harris said in the campaign:
2	A person who bows to the aggressors and tries to be friends with them will lose the trust of allies and cause the United States to lose its influence. Such a person is not worthy of being President of the United States.
3	Following the same logic:
4	A person who bows to the aggressors and tries to be friends with them will lose the trust of allies and cause the United States to lose its influence. Such a person is not worthy of being Statesman of the United States.
5	A person who bows to the aggressors and tries to be friends with them will lose the trust of allies and cause the United States to lose its influence. Such a person is not worthy of being Americans.
6	The evil Japanese invaders invaded China, Australia, the United States, Singapore, Malaysia, South Korea, North Korea, Indonesia, Myanmar, and India. They massacred 51.80 – 89.60 (100.80) million people in China alone, raped and gang-raped 31.45 - 54.4 (61.20) million Chinese women, and plundered 42,000 - 63,000 tons of gold worth \$ 5,289 - 7,933.5 billion, at least 250 million silver coins, looted at least 20 million cultural relics worth 50,000 billion USD, 500,000 kg of natural diamonds worth 132.55-280.5 billion USD, 20 million gemstones such as white jade, sapphire, ruby, and agate worth about 5,000 billion USD, at least 10 million strings of natural pearls worth at least about 800

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	<p>billion USD, at least 200 million tons of rare earth minerals worth 20,000-30,000 billion USD, at least 49,000 tons of bronze worth about 3,535.71 billion USD. Japan committed crimes as the whole nation.</p> <p>If China uses part of the compensation it will receive in the future to thank various countries and people for their support, and gives half of the remaining part to the world's leading countries that uphold justice. Can the United States become the leader of the just nations of the world?</p> <p>Does the United States still want to protect the aggressors?</p> <p>Does the U.S. not want to end the U.S. debt crisis?</p>
7	Why does the United States befriend Japan?
8	Why does the United States still conceal the truth that it did not drop atomic bombs on Japan?
9	<p>Why doesn't the United States help China claim compensation from Japan and force Japan to return the plundered wealth?</p> <p>Much of the property looted by Japan is hidden in secret places. As long as the United States leads countries around the world to force evil Japan to return these properties, the United States will demonstrate global leadership. At the same time, all U.S. debt can be cleared from the rewards obtained from claims. The United States will not be threatened by national debt for a long time in the future. Other countries can also get rewards in return, and the United States can also better display a fair image on a global scale.</p>
10	<p>The social systems of the United States and China are probably just the differences in different periods of the Tang Dynasty in China, not the ideological differences of Marx's utopian communism system.</p> <p>Is it necessary for the United States to confront China?</p>
11	<p>China's science, technology and culture have led the world for eight thousand years. If the United States confronts China, doesn't it seem that American universities do not have history departments and history majors?</p> <p>Doesn't it seem that American universities do not have political economy departments and political economy majors?</p> <p>Doesn't it seem that American universities do not have philosophy departments and philosophy majors?</p> <p>Doesn't it seem that American universities do not have logic disciplines and logic majors?</p>
12	<p>The global production of nuclear weapons has reached 100,000, wasting \$10 trillion. All of this is related to the U.S. concealment of the fact that it did not drop atomic bombs on Hiroshima and Nagasaki during World War II.</p>
13	<p>Mathematically calculated, the two atomic bombs contaminated at least more than half of Japan. On the contrary, U.S. military aircraft were still able to scatter 60 million leaflets over the contaminated land without being threatened by radioactive contamination. Two to three weeks after Hiroshima and Nagasaki, there was no threat from more than a hundred kinds of radioactive substances after the atomic bombings.</p>

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14	<p>Why does the United States still keep the secret that Hiroshima and Nagasaki were not bombed by atomic bombs?</p> <p>The political correctness of American politicians? Have the relevant politicians in the United States not been bribed by Japan with illegal funds? Has the mainstream media in the United States not been bribed by the Japanese?</p> <p>From the perspective of military behavioral economics and national defense behavioral economics, isn't it the case that both the United States and other countries that manufacture nuclear weapons worldwide have suffered significant losses?</p>
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